

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D 5.1

Development of stakeholder performance metrics & System dynamic approach to risk management

Author(s):	Keith Jones, Mariantonietta Morgia, Sólveig Þorvaldsdóttir, Femke Mulder
Responsible Partner:	ARU
Reviewers:	Ivan van Bever, Carmine Galasso, Gemma Cremen
Version:	2.0
Date:	30.09.2020
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments
30.09.2020	2.0	Femke Mulder	

LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
FWCR	Forecasting - Early Warning - Consequence Prediction and Response
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning

RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquakes
PAR	Participatory Action Research
RAIF	Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework
ROR	Relative Overall Resilience
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
TB	Test Bed

INDEX OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	ii
LIST OF PARTNERS	ii
GLOSSARY	ii
INDEX OF CONTENTS	iv
TABLE OF FIGURES	v
TABLE OF TABLES.....	v
1 INTRODUCTION	1
Purpose of this report.....	2
Scope of this document.....	2
Target Audience.....	2
2 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT.....	2
Earthquakes in Europe	2
TURNkey: towards urban community resilience to earthquakes	3
End-user needs & TURNkey proposition.....	6
3 ASSESSING RESILIENCE AND RISK: BASELINE TURNKEY STAKEHOLDERS.....	13
Assessing Earthquake Risk.....	13
Assessing Earthquake Resilience.....	17
4 BUSINESS AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE TO EARTHQUAKE EVENTS	20
Resilience, Vulnerability, Adaptive Capacity and Risk to Earthquakes.....	20
Factors Affecting Business Resilience, Vulnerability, and Adaptive Capacity to Earthquakes.....	23
Toolkits for measuring organisational resilience	31
Measuring Community Resilience: the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities	54
Discussion: Indicators/Metrics for Assessing the Potential Impact of the TURNkey FWRC Platform.....	57
5 CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE.....	58
Evolution of the concepts of risk and resilience applied to critical infrastructures	58
Critical infrastructure as complex systems exposed to threats	59
Frameworks for critical infrastructure resilience assessment and the role of OEF, EEW, and RRE in them	60
OEF	65
EEW.....	65
RRE.....	65
6 SYSTEM DYNAMICS APPROACH.....	66
Introduction.....	66
Methodology.....	67

Systems Thinking	67
System Dynamics	67
Disaster-Function Management Systems (DFM)	68
Municipality Level Resiliency and Recovery as a System Dynamics Problem	69
Research and Modelling Processes.....	70
7 SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS.....	70
8 REFERENCES	71
9 ANNEX A: THE ORGRES TOOL - QUESTIONNAIRE.....	75

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 European Seismic Hazard Map	3
Figure 2: Illustration of the chronological sequence of OEF, EEW and RRE.....	4
Figure 3: TURNkey's consortium partners and testbeds.....	6
Figure 4 High-level end-user requirements against OEF, EEW, RRE chronology (Deliverable 1.5).....	11
Figure 5 The TURNkey proposition (high-level) (Deliverable 1.5).....	12
Figure 6 Resilience as a process (dynamic) and resilience as an outcome/benchmark (static condition). In this figure dynamic features of resilience are blue and static features are yellow. Source: Cutter, 2016.....	21
Figure 7 The relationship between resilience and adaptation (source: Zhou et al. (2016)	22
Figure 8 The Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework (adapted from Morga et al., 2020).....	22
Figure 9 Analytical framework with risk factors grouped by organisational features and characteristics of decision-makers.....	25
Figure 10 Composite Resilience Model, Herringbone Resilience Model, and the Resilience Triangle Model, source: Gibson and Tarrant, 2010	27
Figure 11 Resilience Strategies Model, source: Gibson and Tarrant, 2010.....	28
Figure 12 The Organizational Resilience 'Tension Quadrant' (Source: Denver, 2017).....	30
Figure 13: The REDiTM rating scheme (source: Arup, 2013).....	31
Figure 14 Lifelines appraisal levels under seismic conditions (Kameda, 2000).....	60
Figure 15 Decision contexts for fostering resilience in infrastructure systems (McDaniels et al., 2008)	61
Figure 16 Liquefact Critical Infrastructure resilience tool (Morga et al., 2020).....	62
Figure 17 Community resilience diagrams (Bruneau et al., 2003)	63
Figure 18 Holistic resilience index with hierarchic approach (Fisher et al., 2010)	64
Figure 19 Organizational resilience of critical infrastructures (Brown et al., 2017)	64

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1 TURNkey project objectives.	5
Table 2 End-user requirements - civic protection, first responders and citizens (Deliverable D1.3)	8
Table 3 End-user needs related to critical infrastructure and general business (Deliverable D1.4)	10

Table 4 TURNkey stakeholders' definitions of 'risk'	14
Table 5 Maturity of TURNkey stakeholders in terms of risk assessment	15
Table 6 Average scores for risk assessment, based on an understanding of the construct 'risk' versus measures in place	16
Table 7 TURNkey stakeholders' definitions of 'resilience'	17
Table 8 Maturity of TURNkey stakeholders in terms of resilience assessment	18
Table 9 Average scores for resilience assessment, based on understanding versus measures in place	19
Table 10 Overall respondents' maturity scores based on their risk and resilience assessment scores	19
Table 11 Business disaster preparedness activities (source Han and Nigg (2011).	26
Table 12 Indicators of Relative Overall Resilience (Adapted from McManus 2008) Source: Lee et al. (2013)	29
Table 13 Performance criteria for REDiTM Platinum, Gold and Silver levels (source: Arup, 2013)	32
Table 14 REDiTM Guiding Principles	33
Table 15 TURNkey assessed by the REDiTM criteria	36
Table 16 The UNDRR "Ten Essentials" for Disaster Risk Reduction	38
Table 17 Mapping the business organisation use-cases to the assessment areas in the detailed Business Scorecard.	52
Table 18 Factor 1 Organise for resilience: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities	54
Table 19 Factor 2 Risk Scenarios: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities	55
Table 20 Factor 6 Institutional Capacity: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities	56
Table 21 Factor 7 Societal Capacity: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities	56
Table 22 Factor 9 Disaster Response: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities	57
Table 23 Matrix of Resilience Qualities and infrastructure dimensions (source O'Rourke, 2007)	62
Table 24 Examples of reference modes	69

1 INTRODUCTION

This report describes a desk-based study to outline a framework for assessing and demonstrating the impact of the TURNkey platform on stakeholder and community earthquake resilience. The framework constitutes the theoretical basis for the development of a range of decision support systems (DSS), which will be developed as part of WP5 (in T5.3 and T5.4). It will reflect the latest disaster risk reduction guidance provided by the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (United Nations, 2015). It will be integrated into the TURNkey platform and associated TURNkey decision-making toolbox.

Towards developing this framework, this report has identified metrics to assess how – and to what extent - the impact of physical damage to assets affects the ability of the dependant stakeholders to continue functioning after an emergency situation. These metrics are flexible enough to reflect the different local circumstances encountered in the different testbed (TB) regions (economic, demographic, building topology, etc.) but robust enough to make direct comparisons possible between the different TBs (consistent scales of measurement).

The metrics also allow for ‘what-if’ scenarios to be evaluated, thus assessing how the work of TURNkey WP3 and WP4 would affect stakeholder and community resilience. For this task, existing disaster management approaches of TURNkey TBs have been reviewed, with a focus on how stakeholders conceptualise and assess risk and resilience. These findings are based on questionnaire responses from TBs 1-4 and are presented in section 3. Section 4 reviews the core theoretical constructs that underpin (or are closely interconnected with) organisational resilience – resilience, vulnerability, adaptive capacity and risk. It discusses current approaches and metrics for measuring these constructs, laying the foundation for a framework/toolkit to evaluate the potential impact of the TURNkey platform on stakeholder and community resilience. Section 5 focuses on critical infrastructure (CI) and community resilience. Community resilience relies not only on the inherent attributes of individual stakeholders but also on the inter-relationship and communication between CI and other stakeholders; connectedness is a good indicator for measuring societal resilience, both at stakeholder and community level. The resilience of a system is only as good as its weakest link. This report outlines approaches and metrics for integrating individual stakeholder data into an overall community-level model that will identify how stakeholders’ relationships shape their resilience. This report builds hereby on prior research (e.g. Bartolucci & Jones, 2016, 2017; Jones, 2020; Thorvaldsdottir, 2016), specifically the Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework (RAIF) and Disaster-Function Management Systems (DFM). Finally, the framework and metrics identified/developed in this report are used to assess the draft TURNkey prototype proposition developed for WP1, which is based on end-user requirements (expressed as a series of socio-economic use-cases). In doing so, it shows the value of measures for assessing the impact of the TURNkey platform on stakeholder and community resilience.

This report will:

- Describe the purpose of the TURNkey project (fostering urban earthquake resilience) and the current TURNkey prototype proposition.
- Review TURNkey stakeholders’ current understanding and ways of assessing risk and resilience
- Define the constructs vulnerability, resilience, and risk
- Present a more detailed discussion about measuring resilience
- Show the use and limitations of the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) scorecard for urban resilience for assessing TURNkey’s impact on resilience.
- Present a framework/metrics for assessing critical infrastructure and community resilience.
- Discuss municipality level resiliency and recovery as a system dynamics problem and methods for analysing it as such.
- Discuss next steps

Purpose of this report

This research aims to lay the foundation for a risk/resilience framework that demonstrates/assesses the impact of TURNkey on stakeholder and community resilience. This framework will inform the design of decision support systems and tools aimed at guiding earthquake risk/resilience management. The framework will reflect the latest disaster risk reduction guidance provided through the UNDRR Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (United Nations, 2015). By extension, the framework can also be used by EU, national, regional, and local decision-makers to assess vulnerability, resilience, and adaptive capacity of urban communities to earthquake events.

Scope of this document

This report contributes to research-in-progress. It lays the foundation for the development of a risk/resilience framework and decision-making tools. As such, its insights will be reviewed and modified through the duration of the TURNkey project to reflect emerging issues identified by the research team, project partners; location-specific characteristics of the case study sites; external stakeholders; and expert advice.

Target Audience

Although the report is publicly available it is principally an internal working document intended for the TURNkey project partners and researchers.

2 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Earthquakes in Europe

Earthquakes are one of the most destructive natural phenomena. Between 2000 and 2019, globally more than 800 000 people lost their lives in an earthquake (USGS, 2020). They cause an average of USD 34.5 billion in damages annually (OECD, 2018). A large part of Europe is at risk from earthquake disaster events as shown in the seismic hazard map below. Over the past decade, earthquakes proved to be amongst the most devastating of all European disasters, with almost 19,000 fatalities and direct economic losses of approximately €29 billion (ibid).

Figure 1 European Seismic Hazard Map¹

TURNkey: towards urban community resilience to earthquakes

Although there is increased risk awareness of earthquake events amongst European citizens, businesses, and policymakers, there is limited support available to help mitigate these risks. The TURNkey project seeks to address this shortcoming by developing a Forecasting - Early Warning - Consequence Prediction and Response (FWCR) platform based on a multi-sensor earthquake information system. In developing the FWCR platform, TURNkey will take advantage of the latest developments in Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), also called time-dependent hazard assessment, as well as of Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) and its use, both in real-time (during an event) and in near real-time, when rapidly responding to earthquake impacts (RRE). The focus of TURNkey is to close the gap between theoretical systems and their practical application in Europe to improve seismic resilience before, during, and after a damaging earthquake. The theoretical relationship between OEF, EEW, and RRE systems - expressed as a chronological sequence - is shown in Figure 2.

¹ Source: European Commission (2013)

Figure 2: Illustration of the chronological sequence of OEF, EEW and RRE²

Whilst EEW and OEF systems are still in their early stages of development, particularly in Europe, their potential benefits to society and individuals have been clearly identified. Such benefits range from the preservation of life, through improved public safety, to organisational preparedness to respond to and recover from an earthquake.

Two-way communication will allow the platform to be more effective. People receiving the warnings will be able to provide immediate feedback to the platform. The situational awareness of end-users of the platform will thus be improved. Generally speaking, when alert and warnings are dispatched both to rescuers and citizens, some questions of immediate answers will be provided (e.g., through the crowd-sourcing tools from EMSC and UNIBG³) and according to these answers, other actions will be put in place. To realise these benefits there needs to be a greater understanding of system performance standards from design, through operation to impacts on resilience. Failure to consider these issues as part of the EEW and OEF development process will significantly limit the effectiveness of any measure aimed at improving societal resilience. As such, the first project objective of TURNkey is to develop and validate a robust multi-disciplinary (technical, social, economic) research framework that guides the development of EEW, OEF, and RRE systems (project objectives three, four and five below) and demonstrates how the forecasting and warning systems will improve community resilience to earthquake events across Europe. The objectives of TURNkey are outlined below.

Objectives

The overall goal of TURNkey is to contribute to earthquake risk reduction, by reducing future economic and social losses in Europe and mitigating the direct and indirect consequences of earthquakes. This will be accomplished through the following objectives:

No.	Specific Project Objectives
-----	-----------------------------

² source: extracted from TURNkey project proposal

³ EMSC and UNIBG aggregate in-situ data from citizens affected by earthquakes, through online sources and apps

PO1	To develop and validate a robust multi-disciplinary (technical, social, economic) research framework that guides the development of EEW, OEF, and RRE systems (PO3, PO4, and PO5) and demonstrates how the forecasting and warning systems will improve community resilience to earthquake events across Europe.
PO2	To deploy and improve available instruments for provisions of real-time seismic and geodetic data streams, and implement related monitoring and processing steps in the six geographically- based, and two non-geographically-based, TBs of TURNkey.
PO3	To develop procedures to assess the expected/observed ground motions (ShakeMaps, forecasted and observed) before an earthquake (OEF), during the earthquake but before strong shaking arrives at assets at risk (EEW), and immediately after strong shaking (RRE). These procedures will be implemented within the TURNkey platform (PO6) and applied within the project’s TBs (PO2).
PO4	To develop procedures (automatic computer algorithms based on theoretical models and observed data) for the rapid prediction of losses immediately following an earthquake rupture, while accounting for field observations and structural monitoring to update the models.
PO5	To develop protocols for response, emergency management, and safety communication – including uncertainties (for technical stakeholders, non-technical stakeholders, and the public), based on the decisional rules of Decision Support Systems (DSSs) . The practical implementation of the DSSs will be facilitated by guidelines and protocols to be prepared for safety communication and response.
PO6	To integrate the research, innovation, and methodologies from the outputs of PO1, PO2, PO3, PO4, and PO5 for the development of the TURNkey multi-sensor unit and the cloud-based TURNkey FWCR platform, which will, for the first time, consolidate currently widely-dispersed tools within a ready-to-deploy system, which is also easily customizable, for a tangible real-time earthquake risk reduction.
PO7	To develop best-practice manuals and training materials that, based on stakeholder needs (PO1) and after trialing and improvement through the TB implementations, will be used as a “proof-of-concept” of the TURNkey multi-sensor units and TURNkey platform.

Table 1 TURNkey project objectives.

To reach its ambitious objectives, the TURNkey has brought together a strong multi-disciplinary team of experts (geophysicists/seismologists, geologists, engineers, disaster risk managers, and sociologists) from 21 partner institutions covering 10 EU countries. The platform is being developed in partnership with stakeholders from six European Testbeds (TBs) with different hazards, vulnerability and exposure characteristics, spatial extents, and monitoring networks. The project also incorporates two roaming TBs, one based on crowdsourcing and one for temporary installations. The testbeds are TB-1: Bucharest, Romania; TB-2: Pyrenees, France; TB-3: Towns of Hveragerði and Húsavík (Iceland); TB-4: City of Patras and Aegio region, Greece; TB-5: Ports of Gioia Tauro, Italy; TB-6: Groningen, Netherlands; TB-7: All earthquake affected areas worldwide (virtual TB), and TB-8: EEW system for aftershocks (mobile TB) (see figure below).

Figure 3: TURNkey’s consortium partners and testbeds⁴

Given the different disciplinary backgrounds of the actors involved and the different tasks on which they focus, project partners must work based on a common understanding of the design and operational expectations of the platform. To this end, a draft platform prototype has been developed (as specified in D1.5). described in the next section.

End-user needs & TURNkey proposition

The TURNkey multi-sensor unit and cloud-based FWCR platform brings together EEW/OEF/RRE tools developed across the TURNkey consortium. To assess/demonstrate the potential of the platform

⁴ Distribution of TURNkey’s project consortium partners (white dots) and the locations of the six geographically-based TURNkey Testbeds (TB-1 to TB-6, ellipses), plotted on the SHARE European Seismic Hazard 3

on stakeholder and community resilience, it is necessary to create an overview of how the different models interrelate with each other and with the needs/requirements articulated by the potential end-users of the platform. This clarifies how TURNkey interlinks with the different systems that together shape stakeholder and community resilience. Deliverable 1.5 constitutes a step towards the development of a common understanding of the design and operational expectations of the platform across TURNkey. This high-level outline for a platform prototype is based on the first round of participatory action research (PAR). During this first round, TURNkey researchers worked with stakeholders in the TURNkey TBs to identify end-user requirements of the TURNkey platform. The research focused on civic protection, first responders and citizens (D1.3); and critical infrastructure and general business (D1.4). The tables below summarise the findings of these two deliverables.

Phase	End-user goal	What the TURNkey should deliver
EEW/ RRE	Decision-makers and communicators cut down on time and effort used to collate and process multiple and fragmentary data inputs.	<p>A ground shaking alert (EEW)</p> <p>A dashboard for first responders that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - is user friendly (e.g. Earthquake Cockpit Situation Report) - rapidly populates with information from multiple sources* - presents information that is comprehensive and continuously updated - presents information in a way that facilitates a rapid understanding of the current situation - presents information in a way that enables decision-makers to prioritise interventions and allocate resources accordingly - makes it possible to query information and drill down for detail on a specific area, an element of infrastructure, and critical buildings - enables users to relay information to decision-makers within their organization and other institutional users <p>*Information sources of the platform should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National and international seismic institutes • Local infrastructure and road networks • Critical buildings • Reconnaissance and technical teams • Rescue and other first responder teams
EEW / RRE	End users responsible for alerting key actors cut down in the time and resources required to do so.	<p>An automated real-time alert registry/database for contact points at third party organizations and key personnel that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - end-users can populate/modify beforehand - is linked to TURNkey features such as ‘automatic notification’ or ‘call to action’.
EEW/ RRE	Headquarters can safeguard first responders’ lives by alerting them to dangerous conditions on the ground.	<p>A platform for two-way communication between headquarters and the field that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enables first responders on the ground to assess the degree of danger before accessing collapsed structures

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enables first responders on the ground to leave the building if an aftershock is anticipated - enables first responder decision-makers to communicate instructions aimed at safeguarding rescuers' lives - enables first responder decision-makers to monitor rescuers' wellbeing during operations - incorporates early warning notifications - incorporates aftershock information - has the feature 'rescuer status' <p>The platform should support the two-way sharing of information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impacted buildings • Other critical infrastructure • Incoming aftershocks • Rescuer wellbeing
EEW / RRE	First responders and external organizations involved in the response improve their coordination towards a more effective intervention.	<p>An information/communication platform that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - allows all users to input information - allows all users to access information - alerts external organizations - has an 'earthquake cockpit situation report' feature - has a 'safe areas identification' feature - has a 'damage assessment' feature - allows for eye witness information input - shows the evolution of the rescue operation - enables external organizations to monitor the situation - enables the sending of instructions to external organizations <p>The platform should include information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location and extent of damages, affected areas, and infrastructure viability • Intervention sites and progress on those sites • Ongoing prioritisation exercises

Table 2 End-user requirements - civic protection, first responders and citizens (Deliverable D1.3)

Phase	End-user goal	What TURNkey should deliver
EEW	Minimise direct damage to critical systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidance that supports the integration of EEW with automated organizational systems controlling vulnerable assets, allowing these systems to stop or switch to their fail-safe mode upon receipt of a ground-shaking alert (This depends on the production process). - Guidance on how to incorporate EEW in disaster management and business continuity plans

EEW	Limit injuries amongst employees, customers, and the wider community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidance that supports the integration of EEW with personal ground shaking alerts, carried by individual workers (e.g. employees working in confined spaces, employees operating lifting equipment, employees working at height, and their ground support colleagues). - Guidance that supports the integration of EEW with automated organizational systems controlling critical assets, allowing these systems to stop or switch to their fail-safe mode upon receipt of a ground-shaking alert (e.g. assets controlling hazardous substances or assets moving at high speeds, such as trains). - Guidance on how to incorporate EEW in disaster management and business continuity plans
OEF	Improve employee safety	<p>Issue OEF forecasts, e.g. red, amber, green⁵ (RAG), that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - use metrics and deliver outputs that reflect the organization's needs (e.g. in terms of granularity and triggering thresholds). - are complete, transparent, and timely - communicate uncertainties in both metrics and models - include guidance that supports the development of upstream applications including disaster management and business continuity plans, with a focus on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rescheduling of work tasks in response to an amber/red earthquake forecast. • The conducting of enhanced health and safety checks in response to an amber/red earthquake forecast. • The development of re-storage protocols for safe warehousing in case of an amber/red earthquake forecast.
OEF	Reduce disruption to business	<p>Issue OEF forecasts, e.g. red, amber, green (RAG), that (in addition to the above)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - are designed and rolled out with an awareness of the negative impact that a forecast could have on business organisations. - provide detailed guidance (including possible mitigation actions) and training on how to integrate OEF information into day-to-day decision-making and long-term built asset management planning. - include guidance that supports the development of upstream applications including disaster management and business continuity plans, with a focus on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • having repair teams on stand-by when an amber /red forecast is issued. • testing the readiness of off-site backup systems needs when an amber / red forecast is issued.

⁵ The traffic light system indicates different levels of risk. A red traffic light indicates a high risk, amber a medium risk, and green a low risk. The thresholds for each level may be stakeholder/context specific – and to be determined in partnership with the potential end-users.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> relocating temporary/portable logistics equipment to business vulnerable sites when an amber / red forecast is issued.
OEF	Prevent cascading risks	<p>Issue OEF forecasts, e.g. red, amber, green (RAG), that (in addition to the above)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - allow organisations to examine not only their vulnerability and resilience to earthquakes but also that of their supply chains. - are policy-neutral and operate within a fair and equitable governance framework - guidance produced by OEF systems must reflect statutory and regulatory frameworks within which different organisations operate. - include guidance that supports the development of upstream applications including disaster management and business continuity plans, with a focus on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> joint planning sessions with key business partners, customers, and critical infrastructure providers when an amber / red forecast is issued.

Table 3 End-user needs related to critical infrastructure and general business (Deliverable D1.4)

Figure 4 below maps the end-user requirements against the chronological sequence of OEF, EEW, and RRE depicted in figure 2

Figure 4 High-level end-user requirements against OEF, EEW, RRE chronology (Deliverable 1.5)

NB. The “app” next to the citizen refers to the crowd-sourcing/tasking tools EMSC and UNIBG will develop for the real-time aggregation of in-situ citizen observations.

The end-user requirements outlined above informed a series of discussions with WP leads aimed at developing a common understanding of the design and operational expectations of the TURNkey platform. This resulted in the high-level TURNkey platform prototype, mapped against the OEF, EEW, RRE chronology, presented in figure 4 below. The metrics identified/developed in this report to demonstrate the impact of the potential TURNkey platform on stakeholder and community resilience are based on this high-level proposition.

Figure 5 The TURNkey proposition (high-level) (Deliverable 1.5)

3 ASSESSING RESILIENCE AND RISK: BASELINE TURNKEY STAKEHOLDERS

The previous section outlines what TURNkey stakeholders expressed they expected/required from the TURNkey platform in terms of OEF, EEW, RRE support (see TURNkey deliverables 1.3 and 1.4 for detail). This section outlines what approaches/tools TURNkey stakeholders currently have in place to assess and evaluate earthquake risk and resilience. For this assessment, TURNkey WP leads shared a short questionnaire with TURNkey stakeholders in all TBs. The questionnaire consisted of six open questions. Respondents were asked how they defined the constructs ‘risk’ and ‘resilience’ and what measures/tools they had in place to assess risk and resilience – both for their organisation and for other stakeholders. Besides, stakeholders also provided information on their general disaster risk management (DRM) approaches, some going into great detail. Two WP leads judged that it would be advisable to translate the questionnaire into the local language to facilitate participation - and undertook to do so. To date, seven stakeholders responded from TBs 1-4. Three were government entities (civic protection, municipalities), two were critical infrastructure providers (transport, utilities) and two were critical businesses (insurance provider, school). As this document is in the public domain, respondents have been anonymised. They are referred to as “government A” “government B” etc. Most (five) stakeholders appeared to have fairly mature DRM processes in place. Just over half (four) had an equally mature approach to assessing risk and resilience for their organisation and/or other stakeholders. However, none of the respondents indicated assessing risk or resilience based on a holistic risk/resilience framework, such as recommended by Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (United Nations, 2015). Given the qualitative nature of the open questions and the small sample size, the figures provided below are merely indicative and cannot be generalised. The figures indicate that there is a knowledge/tool gap at the stakeholder level in the TBs and that the TURNkey platform and its accompanying Decision Support Systems (DSSs), guidelines, and protocols could/would be well suited to address.

Assessing Earthquake Risk

The construct ‘risk’ poses a major challenge to earthquake communicators. Even the definition itself is contested. As such, TURNkey stakeholders’ understanding of the meaning of the construct ‘risk’ varied greatly. Table 4 below shows the answers received by the respondents to the question ‘how does your organisation define risk?’ and scores these answers based on the level of understanding they imply.

Scoring

Limited → incorrect understanding or no definition given

Medium → applied / layperson’s understanding

High → formal definition by an official authority

How does your organization define risk?

Level of understanding

Limited (3)	Medium (2)	High (2)
(government A) “Risk = consequences of a natural disaster”	(critical infrastructure A) “The effect the location/type of natural disaster could have on company goals, employee safety, etc”	(government C) Provides formal government definition
(business A) No definition given. Response indicates that they believe risk = natural disaster	(critical infrastructure B) “The possibility/probability that something bad (e.g. injuries, property damage) occurs as a result of human or manmade events”	(business B) “Risk posed by natural hazards is the product of hazard x exposure x vulnerability”
(government B) No definition given – but they point out that historical and statistical data on risk in their region exist – and state that the definition of risk is based on that data.		

Table 4 TURNkey stakeholders' definitions of 'risk'

Answers to the question ‘what formal measures or tools your organization uses to assess risk?’ indicate varying levels of maturity in terms of risk assessment. Given the varying levels of understanding of the construct ‘risk’, this comes as no surprise. It is possible that some respondents simply misunderstood what was meant by ‘formal measures or tools to assess risk’. The answers stakeholders provided are summarised below in table 5.

Scoring

Low / Medium → no detail on if/how they assess risk – or no detail on how they use external hazard information in their own risk assessments.

High → Organisations with more mature approaches had in-house bespoke seismic risk assessment tools and/or based their risk assessments on risk information and guidelines provided by external relevant authorities (e.g. Civic Protection).

Please state what formal measures or tools your organization uses to assess risk?

Level of maturity

Low (14%)	Medium (29%)	High (57%)
<p>(government A) “Research” (no further details) Also – “notifying and alerting stakeholders”</p>	<p>(business A) “The risks arising from natural disasters are assessed by official state announcements (announcements of civic protection), by reputable national and international organizations and research centres” and “The competent personnel team for emergency management of the [business] is responsible for identifying any hazards that exist on the premises and for the preparation of proposals on how to assess them, following guidelines of the [national authority on seismic hazards]”</p>	<p>(government B) “The official measures or tools used by [government B] to assess the risk of natural disasters are the Civic Protection guidelines, as well as the official recommendations of competent services”.</p>
	<p>(critical infrastructure B) “Exhaustive hazard analysis during the design & construction phase to define risks and dangerous situations” (no detail about risk assessments after the design/construction phase)</p>	<p>(critical infrastructure A) “Experience – actual figures and data, as well as estimated damage from possible scenarios” and “Information (including charts and data) from relevant parties, such as Civic Protection”</p>
		<p>(business B) “We measure the risk posed by natural hazards using our own probabilistic seismic risk model. We also use footprints and scenarios to assess other perils”.</p>
		<p>(government C) Developing “a unitary evaluation methodology for disaster risk and a web-GIS platform”, developing “risk assessment and mapping guidelines for disaster management” to be used in “sectoral risk evaluations” by “authorities with responsibilities in the management of various types of risk”. For “risk evaluation for natural disasters” [organisation] “relies on risk evaluations provided by responsible authorities”.</p>

Table 5 Maturity of TURNkey stakeholders in terms of risk assessment

Confirming insights from D1.3, many stakeholders stated that they deferred to responsible authorities – and especially Civic Protection - for risk information/warnings. Research for WP1 showed that end-users require the TURNkey platform to be compatible with existing approaches and local DRM systems (see figures 4 and 5 above). The responses to this questionnaire further suggest that this implies aligning the platform with Civic Protection at the national level.

In table 6 below stakeholders are given an average score for risk assessment based on their understanding of the construct and the measures they have in place (tables 4 and 5).

	Limited understanding risk [0]	Medium understanding risk [1]	High understanding risk [2]
Risk assessment – low maturity [0]	Government A [0]		
Risk assessment – medium maturity [1]	Business A [0.5]	Critical infrastructure B [1]	
Risk assessment high maturity [2]	Government B [1]	Critical infrastructure A [1.5]	Government C [2] Business B [2]

Table 6 Average scores for risk assessment, based on an understanding of the construct 'risk' versus measures in place

Assessing Earthquake Resilience

Unlike with the construct ‘risk’, all respondents appeared to have a correct (if incomplete) understanding of the construct resilience. Over half of respondents had a good grasp of the construct – articulating what it practically meant for their organisations, and they have been placed in the ‘high’ category below. Respondents with only a partial understanding were not completely wrong but focused on only one aspect of resilience, i.e., emotional resilience, resilient design, or the impact of resilience on injuries (see table 6 below).

Scoring

Low-medium → applied / layperson’s understanding (incomplete)

High → applied / layperson’s understanding (adequate for practical application) or formal definition by an official authority

How does your organization define resilience?

Level of understanding

Low-Medium (3)	High (4)	
<p>(government A) “The capacity to detach emotionally from the natural disaster which has occurred, to act consciously”</p>	<p>(critical infrastructure B) “The capability to withstand and be able to maintain service in normal or degraded mode during a relatively long time, following and during adverse situations: technical failures, incidents, accidents, natural hazards, attacks, strikes, etc”.</p>	<p>(government C) “The ability of a system, community or society exposed to a type of risk to withstand a disaster, adapt and restore after it, through maintenance and rehabilitation of structures and restoration of their essential function”.</p>
<p>(government B) “The concept of resilience to natural disasters determines the necessity of the potential losses of a disaster in human lives, at socio-economic and environmental level”.</p>	<p>(business B) “The ability to fulfill our obligations (some of them are set by law) in an extreme catastrophic event. We could also look at it as a business continuity plan”</p>	<p>(critical infrastructure A) “Our capacity to withstand and/or reduce the effects of a natural disaster on the safety of our employees and the public, our operations and commitment to service and our cash flow”.</p>
<p>(business A) “Building construction and design conform to earthquake regulations and the instructions of the fire services and municipality”.</p>		

Table 7 TURNkey stakeholders’ definitions of ‘resilience’

Respondents were asked what measures and tools they used to assess the resilience of their organisation and that of other stakeholders. Over half of respondents gave no information on how their organisation *assessed* resilience, focussing instead on how their organisation tried to *foster* resilience (i.e. they discussed their disaster preparedness efforts). As efforts to foster resilience

indirectly imply some form of assessment, they have been ranked as having a medium level of maturity when it comes to resilience assessments. Respondents who provided concrete ways in which they assess resilience have been ranked as highly mature.

Scoring

Low → no detail on how they assess resilience + no additional information that implies some form of assessment

Medium → no detail on how they assess resilience, but the detail on disaster planning implies some form of assessment

High → detail of concrete ways in which resilience is assessed

Please state what formal measures or tools your organization uses to assess resilience?

Level of maturity

Low (1)	Medium (3)	High (3)
<p>(government A) “Disaster simulations and debates among Emergency Situation Committee members”. For business: “counseling on how emotional resilience can be held under control”. For citizens: “notification and communication”</p>	<p>(business A) No detail is given on how resilience is assessed – instead described risk assessments and detailed disaster preparedness and mitigation efforts.</p>	<p>(government C) “Systematic evaluation of management capacity of emergency situations at national and county level. Future plans: also encourage the voluntary participation of NGOs and private sector in evaluation”</p>
	<p>(government B) A detailed description of the disaster response plan – no info on how resilience is assessed.</p>	<p>(business B) “We work with scenarios and make catastrophe response plans to assess the resilience of our organization, in other words, to estimate the business continuity in an extreme catastrophic event”</p>
	<p>(critical infrastructure B) No detail is given on how resilience is assessed – instead provided an extensive list of safety features in design, safety equipment, disaster preparedness staff, and safety & contingency planning.</p>	<p>(critical infrastructure A) “Actual data and estimates on the system, grid and structural design, human resources (knowledge and location), reserve power capacity and deployment, as well as access to auxiliary power and assistance”</p>

Table 8 Maturity of TURNkey stakeholders in terms of resilience assessment

In table 9 below, stakeholders are given an average score for resilience assessment based on their understanding of the construct and the measures they had in place to evaluate it (tables 7 and 8). Given the qualitative nature of the open questions and the small sample size, the scores are merely indicative and cannot be generalised.

	Low-Medium understanding resilience [1]	High understanding resilience [2]
Resilience assessment – low maturity [0]	Government A [0.5]	
Resilience assessment – medium maturity [1]	Government B [1] Business A [1]	Critical infrastructure B [1.5]
Resilience assessment high maturity [2]		Business B [2] Government C [2] Critical Infrastructure A [2]

Table 9 Average scores for resilience assessment, based on understanding versus measures in place

Table 10 below shows the overall maturity of the seven respondents in terms of risk/resilience assessment. There is a fairly even spread between mature and less mature organisations.

	Resilience Score 0.5	Resilience Score 1	Resilience Score 1.5	Resilience Score 2
Risk Score 0	Government A			
Risk Score 0.5		Business A		
Risk Score 1		Government B	Critical infrastructure B	
Risk Score 1.5				Critical infrastructure A
Risk Score 2				Government C Business B

Table 10 Overall respondents' maturity scores based on their risk and resilience assessment scores

To conclude this section, whilst most (five) of stakeholders appeared to have fairly mature DRM processes in place, just over half (four) had an equally mature approach to assessing risk and resilience for their organisation and/or other stakeholders. However, none of the respondents indicated assessing risk or resilience based on a holistic risk/resilience framework. There is a knowledge/tool gap at the stakeholder level in the TBs and that the TURNkey platform and its accompanying Decision Support Systems (DSSs), guidelines, and protocols could/would be well suited to address. As indicated by stakeholders, these tools would need to be compatible with existing approaches/systems. The responses suggest that this means that TURNkey would need to align itself with Civic Protection at the national level. The next section reviews existing metrics for assessing organisational risk and resilience, as well as the key constructs that underpin it. It aims to identify metrics for evaluating the potential impact of TURNkey could have on stakeholder and community resilience.

4 BUSINESS AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE TO EARTHQUAKE EVENTS

Resilience, Vulnerability, Adaptive Capacity and Risk to Earthquakes

This section of the deliverable aims to identify potential metrics that could be used in the final phase of the participatory action research (PAR) programme, to evaluate the potential impact of the TURNkey FWRC platform on stakeholder' (especially business) and community resilience to an earthquake event. To this end this section will:

- review the concept of resilience, vulnerability, adaptive capacity, and risk to disaster events as they relate to general business organisations;
- identify from previous academic work the factors that affect business resilience, vulnerability, adaptive capacity, and risk to disaster events, and in particular earthquake events;
- evaluate the potential of existing general business organisation resilience, vulnerability, adaptive capacity, and risk toolkits (metrics) to assess the theoretical impact that the TURNkey FWRC use-cases (by reference to Deliverable 1.2 and Deliverable 1.4);
- assess the theoretical impact of the TURNkey FWRC platform on urban community resilience, using the UNDRR Resilience Scorecard for Cities
- outline the next steps required to validate the toolkits/metrics through the PAR program.

The toolkits/metrics identified in this section should be considered indicative and subject to modification/change to reflect feedback on the TURNkey FWRC platform received from the 2nd cycle of the PAR program.

The concept of resilience to disaster events was developed by Holling (1973, 1996, 2001) through a series of studies of how ecological systems respond to external shocks. Holling identified two types of resilience: engineering resilience which considers the behaviour of a system close to its equilibrium point, using the speed of return to the equilibrium position as a measure of the system's resilience; and ecological resilience that considers the potential of a system to reorganise (to a new equilibrium) in response to an external shock, using the magnitude of the shock that the system can absorb before reorganisation occurs as a measure of its resilience. Holling (2001) further argued that, for socio-ecological systems, resilience should be viewed as a complex system that is linked to vulnerability and adaptive capacity and that together these create the environment for either desirable (transformational) or undesirable (destabilising) change in response to a disaster event.

In a more recent review of disaster resilience, Tiernan et al. (2018) considered the relationships between resilience and disaster risk reduction in the context of the UNDRR Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (United Nations, 2015). Tiernan et al. reviewed the development of the resilience concept and concluded that it is best perceived as an overarching term to describe a system's ability to remain stable and recover from an external shock and adapt to new circumstances. Tiernan et al. also highlighted the concept of adaptive resilience alongside engineering resilience as a fundamental aspect of community recovery from a disaster event. A similar distinction between inherent resilience and adaptive resilience was also noted by Cutter et al (2016). The former refers to static features of resilience that can be used to benchmark the inherent (or baseline) resilience within the target or domain area. The latter refers to the dynamic process features of resilience that can be used to assess resilience in the domain area in a post-event context (e.g. the resilience which that developed as a result of socio-ecological processes, such as learning and responding), see figure 6.

Figure 6 Resilience as a process (dynamic) and resilience as an outcome/benchmark (static condition). In this figure dynamic features of resilience are blue and static features are yellow. Source: Cutter, 2016

Whilst neither Holling (1973, 1996, 2001) nor Tiernan et al. (2018) specifically focussed on business organisations, the authors would argue that many businesses exhibit similar characteristics to those used by Holling, Tiernan, and Cutter to develop their understanding of resilience and assess that the general perspectives of resilience would apply. Business organisations combine physical (engineering) assets with social (human) assets to provide goods and services to society through integrated supply and distribution chains. As such, the authors would further argue that business resilience to disaster events needs to be considered from both an engineering and adaptive (socio-ecological) perspective. To this end, the authors would argue that organisational resilience to a disaster event should be viewed as how organisations resist, absorb, accommodate, adapt to, transform and recover from a disaster event (PreventionWeb, 2020) which is very similar to the definition used by the British Standards Institute (Denyer, 2017) in their review of the factors that affect organisational resilience.

Whilst resilience is primarily concerned with how a system prepares for and responds to a disaster event, vulnerability is about the susceptibility of a system to a specific threat (Bakkensen et al, 2016). Vulnerability can be defined as “the conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards” and as such can be related to risk; where risk is the product of hazard, vulnerability, and consequence (Bakkensen et al, 2016). The UN defines disaster risk as the “potential loss of life, injury, or destroyed or damaged assets which could occur to a system, society or a community in a specific period of time, determined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and capacity” (PreventionWeb, 2020). As such, vulnerability can also be viewed as the potential losses that a system would experience as a consequence of a disaster event and can be determined through the use of fragility and vulnerability functions (Murnane et al. 2016).

The relationship between resilience, vulnerability, and adaptive capacity was explored by Zhou et al. (2016), who considered the relationship from the perspective of entities (hazard-affected bodies) exposed to disaster events. Zhou et al. (ibid) argued that vulnerability of an entity is a function of its exposure and sensitivity to the disaster event (hazard), and resilience was associated with the ability of the entity to resist and recover from the impacts (losses) of the disaster event. Zhou et al. (ibid) further argued that in such a system, the role of adaptation is to

reduce vulnerability and/or enhance resilience through interventions that seek to lower disaster risk, losses, or impacts, figure 7.

Figure 7 The relationship between resilience and adaptation (source: Zhou et al. (2016))

Zhou et al's (ibid) model of the relationship between vulnerability resilience and adaptation is similar to the Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework (RAIF) that was developed by the authors in the H2020 LIQUEFACT project for improving resilience to earthquake-induced liquefaction (Morga et al., 2020).

Figure 8 The Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework (adapted from Morga et al., 2020)

The RAIF (figure 8) provides a decision support tool for organisations to (1) assess their antecedent vulnerability and resilience to earthquake-induced liquefaction (the hazard), (2) evaluate the impact (on functional performance) that liquefaction could have on the ability of the organisation to deliver its primary service, and (3) evaluate the effect that a range of physical operational and organisational mitigation (adaptation) interventions could have on either lowering the organisations vulnerability or improving its resilience to an earthquake-induced

liquefaction event. The RAIF also provides a cost-benefit and prioritisation procedure to identify the most effective mitigation interventions and integrate these into business continuity and disaster recovery plans.

The above framework takes a high-level system view of disaster and community resilience. However, business organisations are also systems – and are embedded in systems. As such, the general principles of the framework apply equally to them.

Factors Affecting Business Resilience, Vulnerability, and Adaptive Capacity to Earthquakes

Tierney and Webb (2001) published an early study on business vulnerability to earthquakes and other disasters as part of the University of Delaware Disaster Research Centres preliminary papers series. This work reviewed the results from five studies carried out in the 1990s, which used questionnaire surveys, and in some cases follow-up face-to-face interviews, to identify the factors that help business organisations to cope with disaster events. These studies involved approximately 5000 businesses in total, and particularly focused on how business organisations prepare for and recover from, a disaster event.

With regards to pre-disaster preparation, Tierney and Webb (ibid) found that the majority of businesses did very little to prepare for a disaster event, and any preparations made tended to be low-cost, easy to implement operational interventions, rather than more strategic disaster recovery plans to reduce business disruption and improve post-disaster recovery. Further, Tierney and Webb (ibid) noted that low levels of preparedness were also prevalent amongst business organisations that had high risk perceptions of, or had first-hand experience of, disasters. This was particularly true for small business organisations where constraints of both time and resources often pushed disaster preparedness towards the bottom of the organisations' priority 'to do' list. Large organisations that did have sufficient resources (in particular, human resources) were more likely to have addressed the potential impact of disasters on the business organisation and created roles that focussed directly on disaster preparedness. Tierney and Webb (ibid) also identified the role that the business sector played in levels of preparedness; with business organisations in the finance, insurance, and real estate sectors demonstrating higher levels of preparedness than those in retail and service sectors. This said overall Tierney and Webb's analysis showed that the overall *level* of preparedness had no impact on recovery. What mattered was whether measures that have a direct impact on either short-term or long-term business recovery had been taken.

With regards to business recovery, Tierney and Webb (ibid) concluded that although most businesses did recover from the impacts of a disaster event in a reasonably short time (as self-reported by the business owner), there were several risk factors identified for negative recovery outcomes. These risk factors included:

- organisational size - smaller organisations are less likely to recover from a disaster event; larger organisations appear to inherently more resilient;
- financial condition - whilst recovery outcomes were influenced by the financial state of the business before the disaster event, this relationship was complex. Some businesses that were in a strong financial position before a disaster event reported being no worse off a year after the event, whilst others financially strong organisations took much longer (years) to achieve this position. Conversely, some businesses that were in a poor financial position before a disaster event reported improved performance after the disaster event (mainly in the manufacturing and construction sectors). Thus, whilst the financial condition is related to recovery outcome, Tierney and Webb suggested that it is probably less significant than the general state of the economic sector and wider economic conditions;

- the degree of disruption to business operations - indirect losses as a result of a disruption to business operations - appeared to be more significant than direct losses associated with physical damage and the loss of production. Business disruption resulted from an interruption to supply chains (Tierney, 2007), employee absenteeism (as a consequence of employees dealing with their own domestic consequences of the disaster event), and problems with customers accessing the organisation. Tierney and Webb (ibid) suggested that “the extent to which a disaster creates ongoing operational problems for businesses can be thought of as one measure of disaster severity”;
- damage to the surrounding area - businesses geo-located in areas of high damage tended to be worse off than those in less damaged areas, even if the business itself had not been directly affected by the disaster event, suggesting a degree of interrelationship between business organisations;
- sectoral effects - businesses in the construction and manufacturing sectors often recover quicker than those in other business sectors;
- business market - businesses that had national and international markets tended to recover better than those that relied primarily on their local market; and
- economic conditions - businesses are sensitive to both their sectoral economic climate and the general economic climate.

In drawing general lessons from their analysis, Tierney and Webb (ibid) concluded that “perhaps the most general lessons that can be drawn from research on businesses affected by earthquakes and other disasters is that while much of what businesses experience during and after disasters is the result of firm-level characteristics and decisions made by individual business owners, those experiences are also shaped in very important ways by other forces that are largely beyond the control of individual business owners -such as broader economic trends - and equally important, by what communities do to mitigate, prepare for, respond to, and recover from disasters”.

In a subsequent study, Tierney (2007) expanded on the above and explored in more detail what made some businesses more resilient than others. Tierney (ibid) drew on the work of Rose (cited in Tierney 2007) and Alesch et al. (cited in Tierney 2007) to explore the inherent resilience of business organisations (defined as characteristics that mitigate the effects of disasters on business operations) as well as their adaptive resilience (defined as characteristics that enhance business options and adaptability following a disaster). In exploring business resilience, Tierney (ibid) suggested that inherent business resilience is related to reduced vulnerability (the fewer risk factors an organisation displays, the more resilient it will be to disaster events) and engagement with business continuity and disaster management planning. The focus of this planning should be on reducing exposure and mitigating damage and disruption, rather than on actions to simply improve workplace preparedness. Tierney (ibid) also suggested that inherent resilience is related to the relationship between business disruption and income streams and therefore the impact that disaster events have on the functional performance of the business. Tierney (ibid) suggested that adaptive resilience is related to the business organisation’s ability to contain the negative impacts of a disaster event through mitigations to the organisations supply chain, as well as through innovations that increase the organisations’ response and recovery options in post-disaster conditions. This includes accessing national and local disaster recovery funds. Finally, Tierney (ibid) highlighted the complex nature of post-disaster business recovery by drawing attention to the interrelationships between business sectors, national and regional governments, and local communities - and suggesting that many of the factors that affect business resilience are essentially beyond the control of the individual business organisation.

Han and Nigg (2011) also drew on a detailed study undertaken by University of Delaware Disaster Research Centre combined with a critical review of later literature to develop an analytical framework linking business organisational features and characteristics of business

organisation decision-makers to business disaster preparedness. Whilst Han and Nigg (ibid) confirmed the importance of the risk factors identified above, they also identified attitudes towards risk and risk perception of the business owners (and in particular concern over disaster impact) as important risk factors. Hann and Nigg (ibid) combined the risk factors into an analytical framework, which grouped the risk factors into organisational features and characteristics of decision-makers (figure 9).

To support the framework, Han and Nigg (ibid) derived an index based around 17 activities, (Table 11) Whilst some of the activities now appear a little dated, they are similar in nature to the activities identified by TURNkey researchers in interviews with business and critical infrastructure organisations (Jones et al. 2020), and the index never-the-less represents an early example of a tool to measure business resilience to an earthquake event. Han and Nigg (ibid) applied the index retrospectively to business organisations affected by the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake, applying one point for each activity, to generate a disaster preparedness score (0 to 17) for each organisation.

Figure 9 Analytical framework with risk factors grouped by organisational features and characteristics of decision-makers

Business disaster preparedness activities	
1	Attended meetings all received written information on earthquake preparedness
2	Talk with those working in your business about what to do in the event of an earthquake
3	Purchased earthquake insurance cover damage to your business
4	Purchase business interruption insurance
5	Stored extra fuel or batteries
6	Learned first-aid
7	Obtained a first-aid kit or extra medical supplies
8	Developed a business emergency plan: covering what to do if an earthquake strikes
9	Developed a business disaster recovery plan
10	Conducted earthquake drills and exercises for your employees
11	Being involved in any earthquake preparedness or response training programs for your employees
12	Made arrangements to move the business to another location in case of an earthquake
13	Obtained an emergency generator for use of electrical power fails
14	Purchased a cellular phone for use if the telephone fails
15	Taken action to bray shelves or heavy objects that might move during an earthquake

16	Stored water
17	Had an engineer or other qualified person assess the structural safety of your building for an earthquake

Table 11 Business disaster preparedness activities (source Han and Nigg (2011)).

Han and Nigg (ibid) also developed an index to assess the risk perception of business decision-makers. Based on a 0-3 scale (where 0 represented the lowest likelihood of occurrence/damage - and 3 represented the highest likelihood of occurrence/damage), business decision-makers were asked to score their perception of:

1. the likelihood of a potentially damaging earthquake event (in the next year, next 10 years, next 30 years) and
2. the amount of damage they thought would result from the earthquake.

The product of the perceived probability and perceived severity was used as the basis of the risk perception index. Han and Nigg (ibid) explored the relationships between organisational features, characteristics of decision-makers, and disaster preparedness through 4 regression models. They concluded that an organisation's lifeline losses (electricity, phone, water, sewer, gas) in previous disasters were significant drivers of business disaster preparedness - as were the owners and decision-makers' perception of the risk of future disasters.

In a critique of organisation resilience models, Gibson and Tarrant (2010) explored the dependency between factors associated with organisational resilience to volatile and uncertain conditions (disaster events) and the management of disruption-related risk. Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) identified six key principles of organisational resilience:

1. resilience is an outcome and not a process management system or predictive measurement;
2. resilience is not a constant that can be measured at a single point in time but dynamically varies with context;
3. resilience is not a single trait but a combination of factors;
4. resilience is multidimensional and models of resilience need to view the different aspects of resilience from complementary viewpoints (perspectives);
5. resilience is affected by organisational context, with different organisations demonstrating different levels of resilience (from low resilience [vulnerability] to high resilience [resilient]) to the same disaster event, and different functional units within the same organisation varying in their resilience to different types of disaster events (e.g. amongst different functional units). As such organisational resilience should be viewed as either reactive, prepared, or adaptive;
6. resilience is founded on good risk management that facilitates the assessment, treatment and monitoring, and communication of risk.

Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) used the above principles to identify flaws and weaknesses in organisational resilience models. Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) questioned the logic of measuring a range of attributes at a single point in time and equating these to a measure of resilience, pointing out that the context (e.g. resources, infrastructure, etc) at the time of a disaster event may well be different to those that existed when the attributes were measured; and this difference could either enhance or diminish the organisation's resilience. As such, measuring organisational attributes should be thought of as providing an appreciation of an organisation's resilience capability, whilst its actual resilience depends on how these capabilities respond to the specific context at the time of the disaster event. To this end, Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) argued the role of risk management as a coordinating factor that integrates the different aspects of business continuity management, emergency management, crisis management, and security management with the organisation's strategic objectives and capabilities. Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) also identified the need to consider the 'soft' elements (organisational values, leadership, organisational culture and

capability, communications,) of resilience and how these contribute to an agile organisation that enhances resilience. Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) presented three variants of a combined (hard and soft) resilience model; a composite model in which strategy and policy inform operational characteristics and emergent leadership drive adaptation; a herringbone model in which organisational activities, capabilities, and characteristics that are critical for the organisation to function in normal times can adapt and continue to function in the response to a disaster event; and the resilience triangle model that stresses the importance of continually reviewing, assessing, and adapting each side of the triangle to ensure they are fit for purpose, flexible to changing circumstances, and have the capacity (including redundancy) and tenacity to continue to perform (resistant or stress-tolerant) when exposed to a disaster event (figure 10).

Figure 10 Composite Resilience Model, Herringbone Resilience Model, and the Resilience Triangle Model, source: Gibson and Tarrant, 2010

Finally, Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) identified 4 types of organisational strategies for improving resilience (figure 11). Resistant strategies aim to ensure that an organisation continues to perform as close as possible to 'normal' after a disaster event, by predicting the impact of an event and developing strategies to minimise the impact (e.g. land-use planning, building codes, etc.). Reliability strategies aim to ensure that critical functions, resources, information and infrastructure continue to deliver an 'acceptable' level of performance following a disaster event until full recovery occurs.

Reliability strategies include business continuity planning, having multiple supply chains, and adopting a multimode system where suitable. Redundancy strategies aim to provide alternative approaches (e.g. disaster recovery plans, back-up systems, process workarounds, etc.) to deliver functional performance to an acceptable level. Flexibility strategies aim to provide organisations with the ability to adapt to disaster events by incorporating ‘soft’ issues alongside the ‘hard’ issues that are the focus of resistance, reliability, and redundancy strategies. Flexibility strategies include training and exercises for disaster events and creating an environment for emergent leadership, trust, loyalty, and a unified purpose. Gibson and Tarrant (ibid) conclude that resilient organisations demonstrate a clear understanding of disaster risks (however they are modelled) and the related vulnerabilities, and have a clear strategy of how to respond to these risks.

Figure 11 Resilience Strategies Model, source: Gibson and Tarrant, 2010

Whilst Gibson and Tarrant (2010) reviewed high-level strategies for organisational resilience, Lee et al. (2013) developed an operational tool to help organisations understand their resilience strengths and weaknesses and evaluate the effectiveness of resilience strategies. Lee et al. (ibid) reviewed organisational resilience from four business perspectives: to demonstrate progress towards becoming more resilient; to focus on leading (as opposed to landing) indicators of resilience; to link improvements in organisational resilience with competitiveness, and to demonstrate the business case for resilience investments. In developing their tool, Lee et al. sought to translate complex multidisciplinary sociotechnical phenomena (as they perceived organisational resilience to be) into a set of tangible indicators that organisations could use to assess their resilience. Lee et al used the relative overall resilience (ROR) model developed by McManus (2008) as their starting point. The ROR model comprises three factors: situational awareness; management of key vulnerabilities; and adaptive capacity, which are expressed through 15 indicators.

Resilience ethos ^a		
Commitment to resilience ^a		
Network perspective ^a		
Situational awareness	Management of keystone vulnerabilities	Adaptive capacity
Roles and responsibilities	Planning strategies	Silo mentality
Understanding and analysis of hazards and consequences	Participation in exercises	Communications and relationships
Connectivity awareness	Capability and capacity of internal resources	Strategic vision and outcome expectancy
Insurance awareness	Capability and capacity of external resources	Information and knowledge
Recovery priorities	Organizational connectivity	Leadership, management, and governance structures
Internal and external situation monitoring and reporting ^a	Robust processes for identifying and analysing vulnerabilities ^a	Innovation and creativity ^a
Informed decision making ^a	Staff engagement and involvement ^a	Devolved and responsive decision making ^a
^a Indicators proposed as additions to the McManus model of relative overall resilience		

Table 12 Indicators of Relative Overall Resilience (Adapted from McManus 2008) Source: Lee et al. (2013)

Following a workshop review of the ROR model, one factor (ethos factor) and eight indicators were added to the model (Table 12). Both models were tested on 68 organisations drawn from the Auckland region of New Zealand. A factor analysis of the responses identified a two-factor structure (adaptive capacity and planning), comprising 13 indicators measured through 53 items (questionnaire questions). The adaptive capacity factor accounted for minimisation of silos, internal resources, staff engagement and involvement, information and knowledge, leadership, innovation and creativity, and decision-making. The planning factor included planning strategies, participation exercises, proactive posture, extra resources, and recovery priorities (Lee et al. 2013). The questionnaire is copyright of the Resilient Organisations Research Programme and has therefore not been represented here. However, the latest iteration of the questions (July 2020) in the form of a resilience toolkit can be found at <http://orgrestool.resorgs.org.nz/orgres-tool/>. Annex A shows the result a typical organisation might get.

A more recent state-of-the-art (strategic) review of organisational resilience was undertaken by Denyer (2017) for the British Standards Institute and Cranfield University. Denyer reviewed 181 academic papers and analysed five case studies. to identify the latest thinking in organisational resilience and to develop a methodology (4Sight) for those in leadership roles to introduce and sustain organisational resilience. Denyer (ibid) framed the review against the BS 65000 (2014) definition of organisation resilience "... Anticipate, prepare for, respond and adapt to incremental change and sudden disruptions to survive and prosper". Denyer (ibid) identified

five distinct phases and five contrasting perspectives in organisational resilience thinking over the past 40 years (figure 12). Preventative control focused on protecting an organisation from threats, in supporting recovery to pre-existing equilibria. Mindful action extended preventative control, by stressing the importance of people in recognising and responding to threats, an approach known as ‘bounce forward’ (Denyer, 2017). Performance optimisation extends the ‘bounce forward’ approach by stressing the importance of continually improving service delivery to customers. Adaptive innovation further extends this concept to new markets whilst, finally, paradoxical thinking seeks to balance these approaches, by managing the tensions between them.

Figure 12 The Organizational Resilience 'Tension Quadrant' (Source: Denyer, 2017)

Denyer (ibid) applied a 4Sight methodology to the complex problem of organisational resilience. In the context of a disaster event:

- Foresight is about anticipating potential threats and opportunities to prepare for them;
- Insight is about understanding the interactions between different parts of an organisation and evaluating the impact that potential threats would have on the whole organisation as well as its constituent parts
- Oversight is about identifying an organisation’s critical risks and putting processes in place to manage those risks;
- Hindsight is about learning the lessons from past experiences.

In conclusion, Denyer (ibid) suggests that organisations need to think beyond defensive resilience behaviours to minimise threats and embrace progressive behaviours to adapt to new opportunities. Through this suggestion, Denyer (ibid) recognised the challenge that balancing the two approaches poses to leaders/managers and suggested a 4Sight methodology as a way of changing mindsets.

This section has provided an overview of core constructs that underpin, or are closely linked with, resilience - focusing specifically on general business organisations. The next sections discuss metrics and tools for assessing stakeholder and community resilience.

Toolkits for measuring organisational resilience

In addition to academic studies of organisational resilience, several practical toolkits have been developed to either inform the design of resilient organisations or to assess the level of organisations to disaster events.

REDi™ (Arup, 2013) is a rating system for resilience-based earthquake building design and, although its primary purpose is to inform technical design standards, it also considers the role of organisational resilience in informing design decisions. REDi™ (ibid) seeks to extend earthquake design considerations beyond building code compliance, which focuses on the preservation of life, to include a wider range of resilience and vulnerability issues that affect post-earthquake recovery. REDi™ (ibid) perceives resilience-based design as a holistic process that identifies and mitigates earthquake-induced risks through design to support rapid recovery after an earthquake event. Whilst designing buildings to sustain less damage (to structural and non-structural components and contents) as a consequence of an earthquake event is a key component of resilience-based design, it is not the only consideration. Resilience-based design also considers the impact that the post-earthquake environment could have on the ability of the organisation occupying the building to deliver its primary functions (e.g. damage to adjacent buildings and utility disruption) and to develop contingency plans to manage the external factors.

REDi™ (ibid) identifies a four-category resilience framework (figure 13) as the basis of its rating scheme. The Platinum and Gold tiers aim to reduce earthquake risks (relative to code-designed buildings), by introducing (design) interventions that support immediate re-occupancy status as well as quick functional recovery and low levels of direct financial loss. The Silver tier seeks to reduce damage and support planning measures to reduce functional recovery time to less than six months. For an organisation to be awarded a Platinum, Gold, or Silver rating, they must satisfy the mandatory requirements in each of the resilience design and planning categories, with set objectives in the areas of downtime, direct financial loss, and occupant safety. The performance thresholds for the three tiers are shown in Table 13.

Organizational resilience

Contingency planning for utility disruption and business continuity

Loss Assessment

Evaluate financial losses and downtime to evaluate success of the design and planning measures in meeting the resilience objectives

Building resilience

Minimize expected damage to structural, architectural and MEP components through enhanced design

Ambient resilience

Reduce risks that external earthquake-induced hazards damage building or restrict site access

Figure 13: The REDi™ rating scheme (source: Arup, 2013)

Baseline Resilience Objectives For Design Level Earthquakes		
Platinum	Downtime	Immediate Re-Occupancy (Green Tag ⁶ Expected) & Functional Recovery <72 hours
	Direct Financial Loss	Scenario Expected Loss <2.5%
	Occupant safety	Physical Injury due to failure of building components unlikely
Gold	Downtime	Immediate Re-Occupancy (Green Tag Expected) & Functional Recovery <1 month
	Direct Financial Loss	Scenario Expected Loss <5%
	Occupant safety	Physical injury due to failure of building components unlikely
Silver	Downtime	Re-Occupancy < 6 months (Yellow Tag Possible ⁷) & Functional Recovery < 6 months
	Direct Financial Loss	Scenario Expected Loss <10%
	Occupant safety	Physical injury may occur due to failing components (but not structural collapse). Fatalities are unlikely

Table 13 Performance criteria for REDiTM Platinum, Gold and Silver levels (source: Arup, 2013)

Building resilience issues are primarily associated with engineering solutions for damage control (e.g. base isolation and energy-dissipation systems) or better understanding/prediction (e.g. computer simulations) of structural behaviour in response to large earthquakes (figure 13). Organisational resilience issues are associated with pre-earthquake contingency planning for reducing repair times and minimising the effect of disruption to utilities needed to maintain liveable conditions (for domestic buildings) and support business function (for non-domestic buildings). Ambient resilience issues are associated with the impact of external factors (e.g. damage to surrounding buildings or infrastructure, cascading hazards – liquefaction, tsunamis, etc). Loss assessment issues are associated with identifying the accepted level of losses (direct financial and downtime) and using these to set design criteria for building components and contents. Losses are calculated by predicting the buildings’ earthquake-induced responses (deformations, accelerations, etc.) through computer simulation and using these to assess the level of damage to building components. The implications of the damage (downtime and cost) are calculated using a modified version of FEMA’s PACT methodology (ARUP, 2013) to demonstrate that the design solutions achieve the REDiTM objectives (Almufti and Willford, 2014). In calculating compliance with the REDiTM objectives, predicting downtime remains one of the most difficult and contentious issues (Mieler et al 2018) where simplifications and assumptions affect the accuracy of the predictions. Mieler et al. examined the state-of-the-art of downtime prediction as part of a review of the REDiTM system. Mieler et al. (ibid) identify unrealistic time estimates, both as a consequence of a fraud labour allocation and repair sequence logic as well as the implication that repair times are calculated to achieve full recovery rather than restoring basic functionality to the building. They highlight the latter as the primary concern of the building users - and flag the impact of impeding factors (from initial inspection to the financing and mobilisation of contractors) as critical shortcomings with the FEMA-58 methodology. In response to the shortcomings, Mieler et al (ibid) suggest improvements

⁶ A Green Tag is awarded following inspection by a qualified professional on the basis that any damage to structural and non-structural components is minor and does not pose a threat to life safety and if egress paths are undamaged.

⁷ A Yellow Tag is awarded following inspection by a qualified professional if there is moderate damage that may pose a life-safety risk to occupants.

including closer linking repair classes to specific recovery states (re-occupancy, functionally cover, and full recovery) through fragility curves that relate the percentage of components damaged to the probability of triggering a certain repair class; using cost databases and anecdotal evidence from contractors to reflect local damage conditions and circumstances, and estimating the impact of impeding factors and utility disruption from past experience and expert opinion. Finally, Mieler et al. (ibid) also identified the ongoing challenge of predicting the impact that other systems (e.g. utility systems, building portfolio, healthcare, housing, education et cetera) have on overall organisational resilience and downtime; suggesting that estimates of service disruption might be a better measure than business downtime.

A series of guiding principles (Table 14) and specific criteria were developed to operationalise the REdi™ objectives. The specific criteria are summarised in Table 15, along with an initial assessment of the potential role that the FWRC platform could have on each criterion.

REdi™ Guiding Principles	
Platinum	Enhance the design of the structure and architectural components such that the buildings and contents suffer only minimal (aesthetic) damage
	Provide ‘beyond-code’ provisions for egress systems and other improvements to occupant safety
	Protect MEP components and other critical systems. Provide back-up systems. This enables continued operations of primary functions in the absence of utilities
	Pre-identify contingency plans to provide water and fuel waste removal or employ alternative off-grid technologies in the event of extended utility disruption
	Minimize risk of generally uncontrollable externalities which may affect functionality, including site access restrictions and potential damage from external hazards such as surrounding buildings
Gold	Enhance the design of the structure and architectural components such that the buildings and contents suffer only minimal (aesthetic) damage
	Provide ‘beyond-code’ provisions for egress systems and other improvements to occupant safety
	Protect MEP components and other critical systems or guarantee that they are replaced/repared within 1 month. This enables normal operations to resume once utilities are restored
Silver	Damage to the building may potentially result in a ‘Yellow Tag’, which would prevent re-occupancy until the building is repaired
	Provide ‘beyond-code’ provisions for egress systems and other improvements to occupant safety
	A skilled contractor is required to make repairs to restore the building to a state which can support functional recovery within 6 months. It may be necessary to mitigate ‘impeding factors’ to meet this downtime objective
	The building can resume normal operations only once the building is repaired and utilities are restored

Table 14 REdi™ Guiding Principles

		Criterion (resilience risks)	OEF	EEW	RRE	Comment
Organisational resilience	Resilience planning	Resilience Workshop	Y	Y	Y	Could help frame the discussions on resilience objectives/risk drivers for a resilience plan.
	External utility supply chain	Backup for Utility Lines	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Redundancy Lines	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Off-grid Technology	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Passive Comfort	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Low-use Fixtures	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Gas Shut-off	N	Y	N	Could be used as part of an automated control system
		Backup Communications	N	Y	Y	Could provide an independent communication system for critical workers
		Data protection	Y	Y	N	Could provide advance warning of the need to activate backup/contingency plans
	Security	Y	Y	Y	Could provide advance warning of the need for manual override*	
	Mitigate impeding factors	Post-earthquake inspection	Y	Y	N	Could provide advance warning to place post-earthquake teams on standby
		Contractor / engineer mobilisation	Y	Y	N	Could provide advance warning to place post-earthquake teams on standby
		Access to financing	Y	N	N	Could provide advance warning to ensure post-earthquake finance (e.g. insurance) systems are easily accessible from a technical and human perspective
		Long-lead Time Items	Y	Y	N	Could initiate earthquake 'safe mode' for critical equipment, components, and repair items
		Instrumentation	Y	Y	Y	Site-specific earthquake impact data will be available to inform a 'structural health monitoring' If the building is part of the FWRC network**
	Business continuity	Risk assessment	Y	Y	Y	Could provide logistic mitigation information before and after an earthquake to reduce downtime. It will also indicate damaged assets as part of RRE, to inform business continuity planning
		Food and water	Y	N	N	Advance warning to allow food and water stock levels to be checked and replenished if required
		Preparedness training	Y	N	N	Advance warning to allow first-aid and medical supply stock levels to be checked and replenished if required
	Advocacy for resilience	Improve infrastructure	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal community resilience planning

		Incentives	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal community resilience planning
Building resilience	Seismic hazard	Design level earthquakes	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Site response analysis	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
	Enhanced structural design	Code minimum requirements	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Design demands	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Vertical earthquakes	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Minimise structural damage	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Minimise residual drift	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Expose structural elements	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Symmetric design	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
	Enhanced non-structural design	Minimise non-structural damage	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Equipment functionality	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Location of critical components	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Protect facades	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Anchor heavy building contents	Y	N	N	Check anchorage at times of heightened risk
		Protect other building contents	Y	N	N	Relocate valuable and mission-critical contents to a 'designed safe' area at times of heightened risk
	Capacity design	Superstructure of base isolated buildings	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Capacity of base isolators	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Capacity of viscous dampers	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
	Safer egress	Stairs	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Doors	N	Y	N	Could provide an automatic opening
		Elevators	N	Y	N	Automated return to 'safe' location
	Structural analysis	Non-linear response history	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Simulation model	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
Ground motions		N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design	
Peer review and quality assurance	Structural peer review	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design	
	Non-structural calculations	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design	
	Installation of non-structural components	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design	

		Mechanical electrical and plumbing review	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Design bill components	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
Ambient resilience	Earthquake-induced hazards	Design liquefaction	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		High liquefaction hazard	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Other ground failures	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		High tsunami hazard	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Assessment of surrounding buildings	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		High hazard from surrounding buildings	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Assessment of surrounding nonbuilding structures	Y	Y	N	Could provide advance warning to place critical structures into ‘failsafe’ mode
		Fire sprinklers	Y	N	N	Could provide advance warning to test fire suppressant systems
Loss assessment	General assessment guidelines	Guidelines for loss assessment	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
		Direct financial loss assessment	N	N	N	No additional contribution beyond that associated with normal earthquake design
	Downtime assessment	Valuable building contents	Y	Y	N	Could provide advance warning (or auto shutdown) to allow actions to be taken to reduce the damage valuable building contents (including production facilities and warehousing)
		Downtime assessment	Y	Y	Y	The use of the FWRC platform could change some of the variables used in the PACT calculation This also applies to financial loss assessment
		Impeding factors	Y	Y	N	See previous comments
		Utility disruption	N	N	N	See previous comments
		Long-lead time items	Y	Y	N	See previous comments
Critical building contents	Y	Y	N	See previous comments		

Table 15 TURNkey assessed by the REDiTM criteria

*Not specifically addressed in the use-cases.

**Building health check was a potential future development of the FWRC system

Although the REDi™ process was developed to inform the design of new buildings, its approach is very similar to the previously discussed resilience-enhancing RAIF decision support tool developed in the LIQUEFACT project. As such, the authors would argue that the REDi™ system could be used for a similar purpose. Reverse engineering the technique in applying it to existing buildings should allow the building owner to assess the inherent and adaptive resilience of their built assets to support the organisations’ resilience to an earthquake event. At a minimum, it identifies the resilience risk factors that organisations need to consider when developing disaster management and business continuity plans for an earthquake event. Furthermore, in the context of this deliverable, it provides a set of metrics against which the potential impact of the FWRC can be evaluated.⁸ Table 15 contains an initial mapping of the FWRC platform prototype against each criterion. As described, this draft prototype was informed by use-cases which were developed during PAR cycle 1, based on stakeholder interviews (see TURNkey Deliverable 1.4).

Analysis

The FWRC could have a great impact on organisational resilience. In particular, the OEF and EEW aspects of the platform could provide additional ‘added value’ to many criteria (as outlined in table 15) and reduce their associated resilience risk, provided the platform informed the design criteria. As expected, for modern earthquake-resilient buildings the FWRC would have minimal impact on the building’s physical resilience. Exceptions to this include instances where the OEF triggers advanced checking of compliance with design expectations (e.g. anchorage of heavy contents and protection of mission-critical contents) at a time of heightened risk - or where the EEW triggers the auto-response of doors and elevators to ‘fail-safe’. The FWRC will also have minimal impact on the ambient resilience criterion, except in instances where advanced warning allows critical structures to be placed into fail-safe mode - and/or fire suppression systems to be checked - ahead of a possible earthquake. The RRE aspect of the FWRC platform is not relevant to the majority of the criteria. However, those criteria that it does affect (e.g. backup communications, post-earthquake logistic mitigation, potential structural health monitoring, post-earthquake loss/downtime assessments) are important to the speed of post-earthquake recovery.

Table 17 below maps the TURNkey FWCR against the Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings (2020), to evaluate the potential impact of the platform on stakeholder resilience. UNDRR developed this Scorecard to help building owners operators and managers understand the resilience of their built assets to disaster events. The Scorecard is structured around the “Ten Essentials” for Disaster Risk Reduction (table 16) to provide a holistic assessment of not only the factors that make buildings resilient but also on the interdependencies between buildings and the wider community. To this end, the Scorecard not only considers issues of building strengthening and emergency preparation but also addresses factors such as civic or community engagement. The Scorecard has been developed for a wide range of applications including office accommodation; retail outlets; public facilities; industrial facilities (excluding operational production process equipment); multiunit residential buildings; and building portfolios (e.g. hospitals, universities, office parks, etc.).

⁸ REDi was designed for the US, so may not be compatible with the building codes of Europe

The UNDRR's "Ten Essentials" for Disaster Risk Reduction				
Essential 1: Organise for Resilience	Essential 2: Identify, Understand and Use Current and Future Risk Scenarios	Essential 3: Strengthen Financial Capacity for Resilience	Essential 4: Pursue Resilient Urban Development	Essential 5: Safeguard Natural Buffers
Essential 6: Strengthen Institutional Capacity for Resilience	Essential 7: Increase Social and Cultural Resilience	Essential 8: Increase Infrastructure Resilience	Essential 9: Ensure Effective Disaster Response	Essential 10: Expedite Recovery and Build Back Better
= Governance		= Integrated Planning and Preparation		= Response / Recovery

Table 16 The UNDRR "Ten Essentials" for Disaster Risk Reduction

The Scorecard comprises several sections: a summary scorecard of 33 assessment areas; a detailed scorecard of 116 assessment areas; an action guide; and data gathering spreadsheets. Each assessment area has a 0-5 indicative performance measurement scale, accompanied by qualitative statements about what would typically be expected at each level of performance. The Scorecard assumes that each of the assessment areas is of equal importance to overall building resilience; thus, no weightings are applied to the resilience calculations. If an assessment area does not apply to the building being assessed, it is left blank (in the data gathering spreadsheets) so as not to appear in the final resilience score. In the TURNkey project, the scorecard will be applied to business organisations with and without the input of the FWRC to evaluate the overall impact of the FWRC on each Essential and overall resilience. The first stage in this process has been to map the potential use of the FWRC platform identified in the use-cases developed for business organisations and presented in Deliverable D1.4 (Table 17).

Legend						
	= direct impact	= indirect impact	= no impact			
Area	Subject/Issue (metric)	OEF	EEW	RRE	Potential impact of the TURNkey FWRC Platform	
Essential 1: Organise for resilience						
Planning for resilience	Existence of plans to maintain or improve the building's disaster resilience				No direct impact on the existence of plans but could be part of the plans	
	Participation in programs to develop continuity of operations plans				No direct impact on participation in plans but could be part of the plans	
Organisation, coordination, and participation	Presence of resilience planning and management focus for internal stakeholders				No direct impact	
	Coordination with external stakeholders				Indirect impact on supply and logistics chains	
	Clarity of roles and responsibilities				If integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans	
	Responsibilities for occupant safety				OEF could identify periods of heightened risk where vulnerable scheduled activities could be rescheduled. EEW could provide a few seconds warning to allow drop, cover hold, or more detailed safety plans to be initiated	
	Hazardous materials and equipment				OEF could identify periods of heightened risk where temporary measures could be implemented to reduce the impact of ground shaking. EEW could instigate automatic shutdown	
	Institutional strength				No direct impact	
Routine consideration of resilience issues in all decisions, and track record/momentum	Role of disaster resilience as a decision criterion				OEF and EEW could inform hard and soft mitigation planning and built asset management	
	Track record of momentum				No direct impact	
Essential 2: identify, understand and use current and future risk scenarios						
Threats and risk analysis	Scenario availability				OEF could identify periods of heightened risk at both the organisation and city level	
	Threats and risk analysis				Could inform threats and risk analysis (e.g. severity could be reduced if EEW/OEF was integrated into process management). RRE could also inform risk analysis.	

	Impact of climate change and sea-level rise				Not applicable
	Consideration of combined and multi-hazard risks				No direct impact
	Consistency with city and regional risk scenarios				No direct impact
Specific risks	Risks of fluvial and fluvial flooding				Not applicable
	Risk of coastal storm surge flooding				Not applicable
	Risk of tidal flooding				Not applicable
	Risk of wind				Not applicable
	Risk of extreme weather				Not applicable
	Risk of seismic event				No direct impact on the likelihood of an earthquake but could have an indirect impact on the severity of the event
	Risk of tsunami				Not applicable
	Risk of wildfire				Not applicable
	Risk of hazardous materials incident				OEF and EEW could reduce the impact of an earthquake on hazardous material storage units
	Risk of unwanted intruder or terrorist incidents				Not applicable
	Risk of power failure				OEF and EEW could minimise the impact of power failure through the early deployment of backup systems
	Disruption to transportation routes				OEF could minimise the impact of disruption by placing clean-up and repair teams on standby (or moving them onto site) during times of heightened risk. EEW could be used to shut bridges and stop trains to avoid derailments
	Disruption to water supply				Could minimise the impact of disruption to water supply by increasing stock levels of bottled water (or stored water) on-site during times of heightened risk
Disruption to communications				No direct impact	
Combined risks				No direct impact	
Financial and legal implications	Monetary consequences of building shutdown				OEF and EEW could reduce financial losses by reducing downtime associated with non- structural elements (e.g. business continuity)
	Legal or contractual consequences of building shutdown				OEF and EEW could reduce legal or contractual losses by reducing downtime associated with none structural elements (e.g. business continuity)

	Social and economic consequences of building shutdown				OEF and EEW could reduce social and economic losses by reducing downtime associated with none structural elements (e.g. business continuity)
Essential 3: Strengthen financial capacity for resilience					
Financial planning and budgeting	Understanding of the likely costs to the building owner-manager				Not directly applicable (would be done as part of long-term earthquake risk assessment) but OEF and EEW could be used as part of a mitigation options appraisal process, cost-benefit analysis (CBA) to show reduced losses if FWCR integrated into business continuity planning/disaster management planning. RRE could help to quantify post-earthquake costs to a building owner.
	Presence of a plan or strategy for financing capital resilience improvements				Not directly applicable but OEF and EEW could be used as part of a mitigation options appraisal process CBA to support the business case for capital investment if the FWCR is integrated into the built asset management planning process
	Knowledge of funding sources, including incentives, and the extent to which these have been accessed				Not applicable
	Funding for ongoing upkeep and maintenance				No direct impact but OEF could provide a trigger for pre-earthquake health and safety checks at times of heightened risk
Insurance and contingency,	Insurance cover				No direct impact unless the use of the FWRC could result in lower insurance costs
	Contingency funds to cover cash flow and out-of-pocket needs until pay-out				Not applicable
Essential 4: pursue resilient urban development					
Building code compliance	Current building codes				Not applicable
	Accessibility requirements				No direct impact BUT OEF and EEW could inform short term local solutions to reduce risks to these groups (e.g. alternate work locations at times of higher risks or early warning giving extra time to evacuate a building)
Resilient building standards	Resilient building programs				No direct impact although the use of OEF and EEW could influence non-structural building design decisions
Beyond the building: code development and occupant education	Building code development				Not applicable
	Occupant awareness and education				No direct impact although OEF and EEW will raise awareness over time as it triggers preparatory actions in times of heightened risk
Essential 5: Safeguard natural buffers					
Protection of ecosystem services	Protection of ecosystem services				Not applicable
	Damage to ecosystems				EEW could trigger auto isolation of hazardous chemicals reducing spillage and damage to the ecosystem

Green infrastructure and energy	Green infrastructure				Not applicable
	Energy efficiency/renewable energy				Not applicable
Management of ecosystems impact	Responsible person				Not directly applicable BUT if such a person does exist, they could use OEF to trigger pre-earthquake mitigation measures (e.g. reschedule business operations at times of heightened risk) that reduce operational vulnerability
Essential 6: strengthen institutional capacity for resilience					
Skills and training	Design and construction				Not directly applicable to manager skills BUT OEF and EEW could be used as part of risk assessment to identify vulnerable system components and propose mitigations.
	Scenario planning				Not directly applicable BUT OEF and EEW could be used as part of risk assessment and scenario planning.
	Building management and operations				Not directly applicable to training BUT OEF and EEW could be used as part of disaster management and business continuity plans.
	Backup documentation				OEF could trigger confirm access to backup plans in times of heightened risk
	Collaboration				OEF and RRE could support pre-earthquake coordination and post-earthquake response and recovery
Data and information	Data collection and analysis				FWRC could be integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans
	Digital twin				OEF could provide short-term data on the level of risk. EEW and RRE could provide data for structural health monitoring
Information sharing and inclusion	Planning a construction inclusion-stakeholders				Not applicable
	Resilience plans-internal stakeholders				FWRC could form part of contract compliance for sub-contractors and suppliers as part of an evaluation of the resilience of the organisations supply chain
	Resilience plans-continuity and knowledge transfer				Not applicable
	Integration of planning and prevention into day-to-day business				FWRC can be integrated into day-to-day planning to provide alternative solutions during and after an earthquake.
	Information-Hazard awareness, preparedness, and recovery				FWRC can be used as part of a wider training programme.
Essential 7: increased social and cultural resilience					
Community role of the building	Critical buildings				Not relevant
	Rollers a community shelter				Not relevant

Community engagement	Support for key personnel				OEF can provide advance warning and place key personnel on standby. EEW could warn key personnel of imminent ground shaking
	Where the building is for residential use, in-reach 2 occupants				If FWRC is integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans, these would include discussions with residents on what actions to take (e.g. OEF could trigger an alert to check personal earthquake action plans)
	Where the building is for residential use, mutual support amongst occupants				As above
	Resilience plans-sharing with external stakeholders specifically relevant to the local community				If RRE is integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans, these would include discussions with external stakeholders (e.g. ensuring first responders had knowledge of any vulnerable residents)
	Outreach work in the local community				If FWRC is integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans, these would include discussions with residents as to what actions to take (e.g. OEF could trigger an alert to check personal earthquake action plans)
	Community or city scorecards				No direct impact
Essential 8: increase infrastructure resilience					
Building/facility infrastructure (internal infrastructure)-natural Hazards and severe weather events	Occupant/employee shelter				If OEF and EEW are included in disaster management and business continuity plans, then this could be used to justify temporarily re-designating existing space for this activity.
	Effectiveness of structure and infrastructure management program				
	Flooding hazard: stormwater management				Not applicable
	Flooding hazard: wastewater management				Not applicable
	Coastal and fluvial flooding: protection methods				Not applicable
	Tsunami				Indirectly if the building is on a coastal region prone to earthquake-induced tsunami; in this case, OEF could give advanced warning of raised risks that could trigger preparedness plans
	Seismic hazard				FWRC could inform the design (or major refurbishment) of buildings in line with the REDi™ rating system (Subject to building code compatibility)
	Wind hazard-storms, tornadoes				Not applicable
	Extreme drought (private system)				Not applicable

	Extreme heat				Not applicable
	Winter storm and cold				Not applicable
	Lightning				Not applicable
	Fire hazard: site				Not applicable
	Fire hazard: building				If OEF and EEW are integrated into disaster management and business continuity planning then vulnerable fire hazards could be reduced through auto shut down or rapid response through activating mitigations (fire crews on-site before the earthquake) before the earthquake
	Electric power outage: backup power				If OEF is integrated into disaster management and business continuity planning then backup facilities could be deployed during times of heightened risk
	Electrical power outage hard: climate control				Not applicable
	Communication outage				OEF could allow the early deployment of backup systems in times of heightened risk
Building/facility infrastructure (internal infrastructure)-man-made threats	Hazardous materials: building				OEF could allow enhanced safety checks during periods of heightened risk. EEW could instigate fail-safe protocols
	Hazardous materials-site				No direct impact
	Terrorism				No direct impact although increased security could be initiated in times of heightened risk
Supporting public infrastructure (external infrastructure)	Access-site				RRE could provide real-time updates on critical transportation systems. OEF could initiate temporarily accommodating key recovery personal on-site during periods of raised risk.
	Critical infrastructure				RRE could provide real-time updates on infrastructure systems. OEF could be used to divert delivers/distribution to less risky alternatives during periods of heightened risk. EEW could be used to close critical infrastructure at risk
	Disaster response infrastructure				OEF would allow the deployment of local services to standby readiness - on-site medical centre stocks could be replenished. RRE could provide real-time updates on logistic supply lines
Essential 9: Ensure effective disaster response					
Plans and preparation	Existence and completeness of plans				FWRC needs to be fully integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans
	Integration with intersecting plans and capabilities				FWRC needs to be applied across the supply chain and integrated with wider community resilience plans

	Integration with intersecting plans and capabilities-understanding of others' capabilities				FWRC needs to be integrated with community resilience, response and recovery plans
	Integration with intersecting plans and capabilities-proven consistency and interoperability				FWRC needs to be integrated with community resilience, response and recovery plans
	Business continuity plans				FWRC needs to be fully integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans
Emergency equipment and people readiness	Complete set of emergency equipment				OEF could trigger health and safety checks at times of higher risk
	Checking and reviewing equipment				OEF could trigger checks at times of higher risk
	People readiness				OEF could raise readiness at times of heightened risk. EEW could provide seconds' warning of ground shaking allowing people to mentally prepare and take protective action
	Information-resilience contributions				OEF could be integrated into occupants' responsibilities and contributions, which might temporarily change (e.g. different roles) at times of heightened risk
	Assistance to first responders				RRE could provide real-time information to first responders
Warning systems	Operational warning systems				EEW could be integrated into these to give time for employees to take safety actions. Also, allow automated systems to shut down or fail-safe. OEF could trigger testing of systems at times of heightened risk
Drills and practices	Drills				EEW drills to avoid injuries
Emergency communications	Emergency communications methods				EEW is an emergency communication system. OEF could trigger the activation/deployment of emergency communication systems. RRE could act as a communication dashboard between the business organisation and other stakeholders
Essential 10: expedite recovery and build back better					
Preparedness/planning for post-disaster recovery	Post-disaster recovery planning				RRE could provide real-time updates to support response and recovery, including status updates on critical supply chains required for repair and restart. OEF could trigger some pre-earthquake logistics - temporary power or delivery of critical components for repairing equipment (hospitals) or increased inventory levels (stockpiling). EEW could reduce damage to operational/production facilities by switching them into a 'fail-safe' mode
	Post-disaster response and recovery drills				No direct impact

	Collaboration of building owners/managers				No direct impact
	Recovery tabletop exercises				FWRC could form the basis of earthquake scenarios to test resilience actions
Learning from experience-building back better	Learning from past disasters				No direct impact but FWRC could be used as part of earthquake simulation exercises
	Adequacy prior planning and preparation				FWRC needs to be fully integrated into risk assessments to identify and evaluate mitigation options
	Changes to the building and procedures from previous disasters				No direct impact
	Culture of resilience and safety				Will affect whether an organisation uses the FWRC platform
Building back better	Speed of access to funds				No direct impact
	Speed of access to skills and equipment				OEF could be part of the procurement of services requiring suppliers to adopt a 'standby mode' during periods of heightened risk
	Integration of response and recovery thinking				Integration of the FWRC into disaster management and business continuity planning would support this activity
ACTION GUIDE					
Essential 1: organise for resilience					
Planning for resilience	Create, expand or update resilience plans to address current and future hazards				FWRC platform will provide real-time access levels of risk and early warning of future hazards
	Create, expand a continuity of operations (disaster management and business continuity) plan				FWRC platform could be integral to these plans, reducing the impact that an earthquake has on the organisation and increasing its speed of response and recovery through more coordinated post-earthquake actions
Organisation, coordination, and participation	Designate a single focal point or governing process				No direct impact
	Establish links and coordination/information-sharing arrangements with all relevant internal and external stakeholders				FWRC platform could be applied to the organisations and upstream and downstream logistics to support a coordinated approach to earthquake resilience
	Obtain agreement to clear role and responsibility definitions				No direct impact
Routine consideration of resilience issues in all decisions, and track record/momentum	Restructure business and reporting processes/metrics and incentives to make sure resilience is included in all decisions				FWRC platform can be integrated into routine business practices (e.g. OEF alert status could be considered at regular senior/operational management meetings) and processes (e.g. EEW could automate 'safe-mode' for critical equipment and RRE could help post-earthquake response and recovery coordination)

	Queer process for assimilating new information about risks and distribute to all stakeholders as applicable				As above
Essential 2: identify, understand and use current and future risk scenarios					
Threat and risk analysis	Ensure availability of scenarios address known current and future risks, ideally in the format of “average case” and “worst-case”				FWRC platform can provide forecast information on future risk levels and potential level of severity. RRE can provide information on current risk scenarios after an earthquake has happened
	Execute a threat and risk analysis with expert help is needed				FWRC platform will have no direct impact on threat analysis (this would be done using existing earthquake threat data) but will support risk analysis and an alternative range of short term operational mitigation interventions that could be integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans
	Ensure consistency of assumptions with stakeholder and peer organisations including the city and region				FWRC platform can provide forecast information of future risk level and potentially level of severity that would affect both an organisation’s local (city and region) supply chain and could be integrated into community resilience plans
Specific risks	Understand hazard, exposure, and vulnerability levels concerning specific risks				FWRC platform can provide forecast information on future risk level and potentially level of severity
Financial and legal implications	Understand monetary (e.g. cash flow, lost revenue) and legal implications of building shut down for longer than one month				FWRC platform will have no direct impact on the understanding of losses but could reduce building shutdown period. The RRE methodology can be used to enhance the understanding of losses.
Essential 3: strengthen financial capacity for resilience					
Financial planning and budgeting	Understand likely costs of a disaster to building owner/manager				No direct impact except to inform the business case for potential mitigation actions as part of built asset management plans and help understanding of likely costs
	Create a strategy for financing improvements				No direct impact
	Research all available funding sources (many of which may not be labelled resilience) and planned to access these				No direct impact

	Ensure adequacy of the budget for ongoing maintenance of resilience critical items				No direct impact except to inform the business case for potential mitigation actions as part of built asset management plans
Insurance and contingency,	Confirm insurance amount covered and risks covered, allowing for deductibles				No direct impact
	Confirm availability of contingency funds to tide over until insurance payout				No direct impact except for the possibility of potentially accessing assets (e.g. temporarily converting fixed assets to liquid assets, chasing income from customers, delaying payments to suppliers) at times of heightened risk
Essential 4: pursue resilient urban development					Not applicable
Essential 5: Safeguard natural barriers					
Protection of ecosystem services	Understand where and how the building may damage ecosystem services which have resilience benefits and take steps to mediate or offset such damage				OEF could initiate extra protection (e.g. more resilient temporary storage of hazardous items, rescheduling of business processes likely to create hazards outputs, etc.) at times of heightened risk. EEW could initiate auto shutdown (and potential purging) of hazardous lines at times of heightened risk
Green infrastructure and energy					Not applicable
Management of ecosystems impact					Not applicable
Essential 6: strengthen institutional capacity for resilience					
Skills and training	Ensure availability of skills for managing/monitoring design and construction, scenario planning, building management, and risk/disaster management				FWRC will have no direct impact but will have an indirect impact on informing disaster management and business continuity plans
	Ensure all buildings and building systems documentation is backed up and stored off-site				FWRC could instigate additional off-site backup at times of heightened risk
Data and information	Create systems and processes to collect and analyse data and information on resilience issues; apply these to updating resilience plans regularly				FWRC platform could provide an integrated approach to monitoring changes in risk and resilience

	Digitise building data to enable sharing with other stakeholders and emergency responders				No direct impact although FWRC could integrate with BIM to support structural health monitoring and process management in the future
Information sharing and inclusion	Create mechanisms to readily update all internal and external stakeholders on resilience plans and capabilities				FWRC dashboard could provide real-time updates on alert status and early activation of aspects of the organisation's disaster management and business response and recovery plans (e.g. placing specialist subcontractors required for post-earthquake recovery on-call) during periods of heightened risk
	Create mechanisms to regularly update all internal and external stakeholders on risks, preparation, and response				As above
Essential 7: increased social and cultural resilience					
Community role of the building	Ensure the building will be able to discharge any community function (public shelter, meeting place, public housing, place of worship, school) during and/or after a disaster				FWRC can be integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans to reduce disruption to building functionality during and after an earthquake event
Community engagement	Ensure critical building staff are fully supported (including their homes, families) so that they will be available to operate and restore the building post-disaster				FWRC can provide support to critical staff at times of heightened risk
	Create mechanisms and processes to account for and ensure the safety and support of residential occupants				FWRC can provide support to residents at times of heightened risk
	For buildings with a community role, ensure community leaders and organisations understand resilience plans for the building and any likely limitation; appoint a community liaison person				Not applicable
Essential 8: increase infrastructure resilience					
	Confirm that the building has a safe refuge for occupants in the event of				No direct impact

Building/facility infrastructure-natural Hazards	disasters arising from risks assessed in essential 2-or make alternative plans for occupants				
	Create processes were monitoring ongoing suitability as a refuge in the light of structural or occupancy changes, or external factors such as climate change or changes in the surrounding area				No direct impact
Building/facility infrastructure-man-made threats	Review procedures for handling hazardous materials, if applicable				OEF could initiate extra protection (e.g. more resilient temporary storage of hazardous items, rescheduling of business processes likely to create hazards outputs etc.) at times of heightened risk. EEW could initiate auto shutdown (and potential purging) of hazardous lines at times of heightened risk
	Review physical security measures that protect against terrorism				No direct impact except that security staff could be relocated to site at times of heightened risk
Supporting public infrastructure	Confirm likely access to roads and transportation systems leading to and from the building				RRE dashboard provides real-time information during the response and recovery period
	Understand likely resilience of key local and regional infrastructures in the event of disaster arising from risks in essential 2, and likely impact on building performance and business continuity				No direct impact although the issues will have to be addressed if FWRC is integrated into disaster management and business continuity plans
	Understanding capabilities and likely response times of disaster response systems (police, fire, ambulance) in the event of a disaster arising from risks in essential 2, and factor into disaster planning				RRE dashboard provides real-time information during the response and recovery period
Essential 9: ensure effective disaster response					
Post-disaster recovery planning	Create a plan for post-disaster resumption of normal activity in the building-assessing and reporting				FWRC can accelerate response and recovery by reducing the impact of the earthquake on functional performance and providing real-time information during the response and recovery period

	damage, restarting key systems, restocking inventory, moving occupants back in, securing repair funds, and so on				
	Ensure those plans are coordinated with other relevant entities and stakeholders, and that they are shown to be interoperable				No direct impact, except where FWRC is required for the organisation's upstream and downstream logistics suppliers integration into community resilience plans
Emergency equipment and people readiness	Ensure complete and reliable set of emergency equipment, with process to ensure frequent checks and reviews				FWRC can instigate checks and reviews at times of heightened risk
	Ensure key disaster response roles are fully staffed and documented and actors regularly trained				No direct impact, except to provide updates during periods of heightened risk
	Ensuring building occupants understand the roles and responsibilities in the event of a disaster, and their understanding is regularly refreshed				As above
Warning systems	Provide warning systems that can reach all part of the building and test these regularly				FWRC can provide warnings of periods of heightened risk and imminent ground shaking, including personalised warnings to employees that are at the greatest H&S risk
Drills and practices	Hold regular (at least annually) drills and practices for disaster response processes and all occupants and stakeholders				No direct impact
Emergency communications	Ensure multiple methods of communication available between building owners/managers, staff, occupants, first responders, and disaster management teams				FWRC dashboard can provide real-time information during the earthquake response and recovery period
Essential 10: expedite recovery and build back better					

Post-disaster recovery planning	Create plan for post-disaster resumption of normal activity in the building-assessing and reporting damage, restarting key systems, restocking inventory, moving occupants back in, securing repair funds, and so on				FWRC can accelerate response and recovery, by reducing the impact of the earthquake on functional performance and providing real-time information during the response and recovery period
	Practices and drills for these plans, just as for disaster response, with internal and external stakeholders, including tabletop exercise with the city				No direct impact except FWRC is required for the organisations upstream' and downstream logistics suppliers integration into community resilience plans
	Ensure presentation of building owners/managers in city and state post-disaster response and recovery planning				No direct impact
Learning from experience	Create a process to ensure lessons and data from prior disasters are included in resilience, disaster response, and post-disaster plans				No direct impact
Building back faster	Confirm the funding for repairs and resumption of business activity can be accessed in time to prevent undue financial loss or displacement				FWRC can identify the need confirm access to liquid assets is available and essential staff/subcontractors are placed 'on-call' during periods of heightened risk
	Confirm speed of access to necessary skills and equipment				FWRC can place essential staff/subcontractors 'on-call' and instigate pre-earthquake redeployment of temporary facilities (e.g. move and connect temporary power generators to critical business locations) during periods of heightened risk

Table 17 Mapping the business organisation use-cases to the assessment areas in the detailed Business Scorecard.

Whilst toolkits like REDi™ and the UNDRR Score Card use a metric-based approach to assess the resilience of organisations to disaster events, other toolkits use a checklist approach to help organisations assess their disaster risks and develop mitigation and recovery plans.

The Emergency Preparedness for Industry and Commerce Council (2003) produced an Earthquake Planning for Business guide for British Columbia based around a series of checklists for preparedness, mitigation, response, and recovery to earthquakes that seek to minimize life, property, and economic losses. Each checklist comprises a set of yes/no questions (except for the response phase, for which there is specific guidance on what to do during an earthquake) that lead the organisation through a series of physical (e.g. building design and operation), operational (e.g. business planning and service delivery/production) and organisational (e.g. financial and legal/regulatory) issues to support the writing of an emergency plan. FEMA's QuakeSmart Business Toolkit (2008) is another checklist-based approach to earthquake risk reduction. QuakeSmart uses a series of checklist and templates to help business organisations identify and implement earthquake mitigation interventions to reduce disruption, damage or losses (business, human, building, and contents) to an earthquake event. Again, the checklist approach is used to identify potential risks whilst a template is used to assign potential mitigation solutions (structural, non-structural, fixtures and fittings, operational, etc) to each risk and to support action planning. A more practical set of disaster resilience guidance is provided by the Earthquake County Alliance (2016) booklet "7 Steps To a Disaster Resilient Workplace", to help business organisations prepare for and recover from an earthquake event. The booklet uses a checklist-based approach for business organisations to identify potential hazards (internal and external) and the organisations' critical business assets (people, data, operations, inventory, equipment, buildings) and then uses a risk matrix to score the impact (negligible, marginal, critical, or catastrophic impact) that an earthquake would have on each critical asset. The booklet then suggests a range of mitigations (similar to those suggested by QuakeSmart) that the organisation can apply to their most vulnerable assets.

Finally, several theoretical models of business organisation vulnerability and resilience to disaster events have been developed over the past few years. Birkmann (2013) produced a comprehensive study of the issues associated with measuring vulnerability to natural hazards and their contribution to disaster resilient societies. Birkmann (ibid) explored the concept of vulnerability - from the perspective of vulnerability as an internal risk factor associated with the intrinsic characteristics of the system at risk – to a multidimensional view of vulnerability, in which the construct is framed within a wider physical, economic, social, environmental and institutional perspective. In exploring the different spheres of vulnerability, Birkmann (ibid) identified the difficulty in operationalising vulnerability into a series of indicators that could be applicable across all. He concludes that it was probably not possible to develop a single governing equation or vulnerability measure that could be applied at all levels and to all hazards. As such Birkmann (ibid) identified the need for indicators to reflect the specific context to which they are applied, outlining a six-phase process for their development and assessment:

1. define goals (its objectives) and clarify the scope of the indicator (its function);
2. identify a conceptual framework (factor-based, sector-based, etc.);
3. define selection criteria (accuracy and availability of data);
4. identify potential indicators;
5. evaluate potential indicators against objectives and function;
6. analyse indicator results and assess indicator performance.

Measuring Community Resilience: the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities

The UNDRR also developed a disaster resilience scorecard for cities. As with the Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings, it is structured around the “Ten Essentials” for Disaster Risk Reduction (table 16). The Scorecard provides a set of assessments that will allow local governments to monitor and review progress and challenges in the implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 (United Nations, 2015), and assess their disaster resilience. Tables 18-22 below review the Essentials that TURNkey could potentially contribute towards. TURNkey has no impact on the following Essentials for Making Cities Resilient:

- Factor - 3.0 Strengthen Financial Capacity for Resilience
- Factor - 4.0 Pursue Resilient Urban Development
- Factor – 5.0 Safeguard Natural Buffers to Enhance the Protective Functions Offered by Natural Ecosystems
- Factor - 10.0 Expedite Recovery and Build Back Better

TURNkey does have a potential impact on Factor 8.0 (Increase Infrastructure resilience). However, the metrics the UNDRR Score Card lists for this Factor do not assess this impact well. Alternative metrics are provided in the section “Critical Infrastructure and Community Resilience”.

Factor: 1.0 Organise for resilience					
Metric	Detail	Potential Impact of FWRC			Relevant features FWCR
		OEF	EEW	RRE	
1.1 Plan Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk consideration in Plan Making • Review of strategic plans 			Yes	TURNkey Business Continuity and Resilience Plan + Disaster Management Plan Framework
1.2 Organization, coordination and participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-event planning and preparation • Co-ordination of event response 	Yes		Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit TURNkey Business Continuity and Resilience Plan + Disaster Management Plan Framework
1.4 Data capture, publication, and sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extent to which data on the city’s resilience position is shared with other organizations involved with the city’s resilience 			Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit

Table 18 Factor 1 Organise for resilience: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities

Factor: 2.0 Identify, Understand and Use Current and Future Risk Scenarios					
Metric	Detail	Potential Impact of FWRC			Relevant features FWCR
		OEF	EEW	RRE	
2.1 Hazard Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of hazards (also called perils, or shocks and stresses) that the city faces, and their likelihood • Knowledge of exposure and vulnerability • Damage and loss estimation 	Yes	Yes	Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit
2.2 Knowledge of exposure and consequence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of exposure and vulnerability • Damage and loss estimation 	Yes	Yes	Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit
2.4 Hazard maps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of hazard maps (for example, flood or seismic risk maps) 	Yes	Yes		TURNkey earthquake info cockpit
2.5 Updating of scenario, risk, vulnerability, and exposure information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequent and complete updates of scenarios. • Agreed process (incl. all relevant agencies) to • Update hazard estimates every 3 years or less • Update exposure and vulnerability assessments and asset inventory every 18 months or less 	Yes		Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit

Table 19 Factor 2 Risk Scenarios: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities

Factor: 6.0 Strengthen Institutional Capacity for Resilience					
Metric	Detail	Potential Impact of FWRC			Relevant features FWCR
		OEF	EEW	RRE	

6.3 Data capture, publication, and sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The extent to which data on the city’s resilience position is shared with other organizations involved with the city’s resilience The extent to which data on the city’s resilience position is shared with the community organizations and public 			Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit Smartphone app for communities
--	---	--	--	-----	---

Table 20 Factor 6 Institutional Capacity: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities

Factor: 7.0 Understand and Strengthen Societal Capacity for Resilience					
Metric	Detail	Potential Impact of FWRC			Relevant features FWCR
		OEF	EEW	RRE	
7.3 Private sector/employers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business continuity planning 	Yes	Yes	Yes	TURNkey Business Continuity and Resilience Plan + Disaster Management Plan Framework
7.4 Citizen engagement techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of mobile and e-mail “systems of engagement” to enable citizens to receive and give updates before and after a disaster 		Yes	Yes	Smartphone app for communities

Table 21 Factor 7 Societal Capacity: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities

Factor: 9.0 Ensure Effective Disaster Response					
Metric	Detail	Potential Impact of FWRC			Relevant features FWCR
		OEF	EEW	RRE	
9.1 Early warning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existence and effectiveness of early warning systems Reach of warning 	Yes	Yes		TURNkey earthquake info cockpit Smartphone app for communities

9.2 Event response plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of emergency response plans that integrate professional responders and community organizations 			Yes	TURNkey Business Continuity and Resilience Plan + Disaster Management Plan Framework
9.6 Interoperability and inter-agency working	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability with neighbouring cities/states and other levels of government of critical systems and procedures • Emergency operations centre • Coordination of post-event recovery 			Yes	TURNkey earthquake info cockpit TURNkey Business Continuity and Resilience Plan + Disaster Management Plan Framework

Table 22 Factor 9 Disaster Response: Mapping the TURNkey features against the UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities

Discussion: Indicators/Metrics for Assessing the Potential Impact of the TURNkey FWRC Platform

This deliverable aims to identify factors and models that adequately measure organisational and community resilience to earthquake events - and to evaluate the potential of current resilience toolkits to assess the impact of the FWRC platform on stakeholder and community resilience. This section has shown that resilience is shaped by a combination of physical, organisational, operational, and governance factors. The REDi™ rating system and UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings cover organisational resilience. The UNDRR Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities covers community resilience. Given that no single metric can assess resilience by itself, TURNkey metrics will cover a range of quantitative and qualitative factors. The role of TURNkey in fostering stakeholder and community resilience (as currently specified in the TURNkey platform prototype proposition) is not to provide ‘hard’ mitigation in terms of the physical performance of built assets, but to support a series of ‘soft’ mitigation interventions to reduce disaster risk. The metrics should cover both the direct and indirect impacts of TURNkey on DRR processes and practices that foster resilience. An example of an indirect impact would be the fostering of resilience through raising awareness. The focus of the metrics to be used by TURNkey - the UNDRR scorecards and REDi™ rating system – specifically focus on risk reduction. Because the scorecards and rating systems were developed before OEF/EEW were widely available, they do not consider their role in earthquake DRR. This section has mapped the TURNkey prototype proposition (informed by end-user use cases) to the scorecard and rating system metrics. These will be validated during the PAR. Where these metrics fall short in assessing TURNkey’s impact, new metrics will be developed.

5 CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE

Evolution of the concepts of risk and resilience applied to critical infrastructures

Several general definitions have been provided for risk and vulnerability in the last decades. All of them identify risk as a consequence of vulnerability. The most applied definition of risk was proposed by UNDRO, 1980, which indicates risk (R) as a combination of hazard (H), vulnerability (V), and exposure, i.e. elements at risk, (E): $R=H*V*E$. While this definition distinguishes vulnerability and exposure, Scholz et al., 2012 define vulnerability as the indicator for exposure and sensitivity to loss. A more complex definition of vulnerability is presented in the study of McCarthy et al., 2001, as it is indicated to be a function of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity of a system. This definition introduces the time-variant characteristic of complex system vulnerability. This changes the risk definition from the static condition of a system for which losses are assessed and solutions are proposed in terms of preferences or utility functions (Scholz et al., 2012), to time evolution of the response of the system to a threat. Hosseini et al., 2016 proposed a collection of definitions of system resilience, which can be summarized as “the ability of a system to respond to a threatening event”. In some of those definitions, it is clear that it is a dynamic aspect of this system's ability.

On the other hand, Scholz et al., 2012 pointed out that the concepts of resilience and risk merge when are assessed for a complex system that does not measure the potential losses of a specific category of good, item, or infrastructure, but the outcomes to a complex reality that include several elements interconnected one to each other. To support the equivalence of risk and resilience, Scholz et al., 2012 define adaptive capacity as the extent to which a complex system can sustain the damage. In that sense, adaptive capacity is the inverse of the vulnerability of the system. Proag, 2014 defines adaptive capacity as the property of a system that adapts to a disruptive event and clearly distinguishes it from restorative capacity, which is the ability of a system to recover; whilst Lee et al., 2013 indicate adaptivity as the ability of a system to restore its functionality and develop new capabilities.

All system resilience definitions refer to the key concept of system functionality that is related to system resilience assessment. Chang et al., 2014 implicitly define resilience, although their work is about risk. In fact, in the risk assessment they include includes the concepts shock absorption and system functionality and indicates service disruption and recovery over time, which respectively are indicated as functionality loss and time needed to restore the functionality in most of the resilience definitions, while Bruneau et al., 2003 indicate that infrastructure functionality both during and after an event is critical to achieving a quick return of a community to pre-disaster normal condition.

In more engineering contexts, the functionality measured at different times during a disaster or its evolution is interpreted as a resilience measure. Holling, 1996 defined “engineering resilience” as the measure of system functionality for which a single equilibrium point can be defined and that is characterized by efficiency, constancy, and predictability. In contrast to this mono-dimensional definition of resilience applicable to simplified systems, Holling, 1996 presented the concept of the ecological resilience of a system, which is characterized by several equilibrium points and involves concepts such as persistence, change, and unpredictability. Such resilience is assessed for systems that are complex and include components of different kinds linked to each other in a complex way, which are indicated as a system of systems. Besides several kinds of components, a complex system is characterized by a variety of definitions of functionality, which are called system dimensions by some authors, such as O’Rourke, 2007; Morga et al., 2020.

Critical infrastructure as complex systems exposed to threats

The literature identifies community and cities as the most complex systems of systems threatened by natural hazards. By defining city resilience, Chang et al., 2014 state that the post-shock functionality of cities is related to the functionality of infrastructures and show that intrinsic barriers can inhibit actions at the community level aiming to maintain a system of systems functionality. The complexity of a system of systems is even more evident considering the interdependence of infrastructures indicated by studies such as Chang et al, 2014 and Fisher et al., 2010. Chang et al., define infrastructures in terms of business; whilst Brown et al., 2017 highlight the organizational dimension of critical infrastructures. In reference to organizations, Lee et al., 2013 define resilience as a multi-dimensional and sociotechnical phenomenon that addresses how people manage uncertainty. A wider interpretation of this definition indicates that resilience is not an inherent characteristic or ability of a system. Thinking of critical infrastructures as systems that include technical and organizational dimensions, their resilience must be assessed using a set of indicators, which cannot be easily combined in a functionality or resilience index that fits an engineering resilience curve. Among the indicators measuring infrastructure failure in terms of business, Chang et al., 2014 identify information sharing and lack of experience in dealing with specific disasters (which Morga et al., defined as the ability to learn from others). This latest definition indicates the pro-active aspect of the socio-organizational dimension of a complex system, such as infrastructure. This pro-active attitude to overcome a threat indicates that often disaster can be avoided through risk management plans. Scholz et al, 2012 distinguish between avoidable and not-avoidable risk, by referring to Luhmann's study about risk and danger. Applying the definition given by Luhmann to the risk assessment of critical infrastructure, it is clear that whilst the management team deals with the risk assessment of the infrastructures and takes decisions regarding which mitigation options to apply, infrastructure employees are exposed to danger. In that sense, there is active and passive exposure to risk and losses within the socio-organizational dimension of critical infrastructure. For this reason, a large portion of critical infrastructure employees are defined as "human assets", and their losses during disasters are measured like "built asset" losses by assigning a monetary value. This dual active-passive view of risk assessment and mitigation is in line with the common top-down approach of decision making for risk management. On the contrary, the assessment of the organizational resilience of critical infrastructures proposed by Brown et al., highlights a more pro-active bottom-up approach to deal with disasters, which is typical of the adaptivity aspect of the resilience.

Per the approach proposed in the literature that identifies several dimensions of critical infrastructure, Proag, 2014 distinguishes between hard and soft resilience. Soft resilience indicates the direct change of structures and institutions due to a threatening event, and hard resilience is the infrastructure's ability to absorb the impact and recover without fundamental changes. The adjectives "hard" and "soft" were used in the literature to indicate different kinds of infrastructures, while their resilience assessment is equivalent. Omer et al., 2014 and Morga et al., 2020 define soft infrastructures as all institutions and enterprises critical to the social and economic life of a community; while Morga et al., 2020 defines hard infrastructures as physical systems needed for community life, which include lifelines, i.e. horizontal infrastructures required during the disaster management and recovery phase. Morga et al., 2020 further clarify that no infrastructure can be classified as "purely hard" or "purely soft", but all are a mixture of hard and soft components.

Frameworks for critical infrastructure resilience assessment and the role of OEF, EEW, and RRE in them

Regarding the methodology used to assess systems resilience, Hosseini et al. 2016 define two main categories, i.e., qualitative and quantitative methods. Hosseini et al. 2016 further classify the qualitative methods as conceptual frameworks and semi-quantitative indices, and the quantitative methods as generic system resilience assessment in terms of functionality and structural-based quantitative methods combining more indicators. Whilst generic system resilience assessment methods focus on the assessment of the deviation of the infrastructure functionality from the equilibrium condition due to a threat, structural-based methods use multi-criteria optimization methods or combine specific indices for each kind of infrastructure component. The structural-based method proposed by Kameda, 2000 (see Figure 14) identifies three system levels: component, system, and societal. The third resilience assessment level is mostly related to post-event recovery and disruption acceptance by the community (Davis and Giovinazzi, 2015).

Figure 14 Lifelines appraisal levels under seismic conditions (Kameda, 2000)

Qualitative frameworks, such as the one proposed by McDaniels et al., 2008 (see Figure 15) assess the resilience of complex systems.

Figure 15 Decision contexts for fostering resilience in infrastructure systems (McDaniels et al., 2008)

Semi-quantitative methods had been successfully applied to assess critical infrastructure resilience, as they summarize an assessment of resilience qualities (such as Robustness, Redundancy, Resourcefulness, and Rapidity in O’Rourke, 2007 and Bruneau et al., 2003 – See Table 24) or resilience aspects (such as in Morga et al., 2020 – see Figure 16) for each dimension of critical infrastructure. Whilst Morga et al., identify the Organizational, Technical, and Operational infrastructure resilience dimensions, O’Rourke, 2007 indicates four infrastructure resilience dimensions: Technical, Organizational, Social, and Economic. Bruneau et al., associate Technical and Organizational dimensions and Social and Economic dimensions together. While the first couple (Technical and Organizational) is related to the infrastructure’s physical capacity to operate as before the disaster, the second one (Social and Economic) examines social and economic infrastructure performance concerning the community’s capacity to recover from the disaster. This dichotomy between ex-ante and ex-post resilience assessment is clear in the community resilience framework proposed by Bruneau et al., 2003 (see Figure 17). The dichotomy of ex-ante and ex-post infrastructure resilience assessment is also included in the qualitative framework proposed by McDaniels et al., 2008. The dual resilience assessment aspect proposed by Bruneau et al., 2003; McDaniels et al., 2008 is neglected by Morga et al., 2020, which proposes the resilience aspect as the evolution over time of infrastructure functionality phases, from before to after the disaster occurrence.

Table 23 Matrix of Resilience Qualities and infrastructure dimensions (source O'Rourke, 2007)

Dimension/Quality	Technical	Organizational	Social	Economic
Robustness	Building codes and construction procedures for new and retrofitted structures	Emergency operations planning	Social vulnerability and degree of community preparedness	Extent of regional economic diversification
Redundancy	Capacity for technical substitutions and "work-arounds"	Alternate sites for managing disaster operations	Availability of housing options for disaster victims	Ability to substitute and conserve needed inputs
Resourcefulness	Availability of equipment and materials for restoration and repair	Capacity to improvise, innovate, and expand operations	Capacity to address human needs	Business and industry capacity to improvise
Rapidity	System downtime, restoration time	Time between impact and early recovery	Time to restore lifeline services	Time to regain capacity, lost revenue

Figure 16 Liquefact Critical Infrastructure resilience tool (Morga et al., 2020)

Figure 17 Community resilience diagrams (Bruneau et al., 2003)

A simpler tool for critical infrastructure resilience assessment was proposed by Fisher et al., 2010 (see Figure 18). While this tool only identifies dimensions of critical infrastructures, it also highlights their interdependence. Another simple tool for infrastructure resilience assessment is the CI-RAT tool proposed by the European project ResiLens (Resilens. Deliverable 2.2, 2016), which classifies resilience indicators according to three domains: Organizational, Social, and Technological.

An even simpler semi-quantitative method is proposed by Brown et al., 2017, which focuses only on measuring the organizational resilience of critical infrastructures (see Figure 19).

Figure 18 Holistic resilience index with hierarchic approach (Fisher et al., 2010)

Resilience Indicators

Figure 19 Organizational resilience of critical infrastructures (Brown et al., 2017)

None of the resilience assessment frameworks proposed in the literature and analysed in this section clearly identify indicators strictly related to OEF, EEW and RRE. Therefore, there is a need to identify each of those elements concerning the aspects and dimensions of infrastructure resilience proposed by Morga et al., 2020.

OEF

OEF is a risk-mitigation measure that acts before the seismic event and influences the short-term pre-event preparedness. In particular, it affects the operational aspects of preparedness:

- Planned contingency (i.e. resources storing),
- Planned redundancy (i.e. appraisal of the redundancy functionality);

It also affects organizational aspects of the absorption:

- Security procedures (i.e. alert procedure activation)
- Communication (i.e. communication of security, evacuation procedures)
- Leadership (i.e. implementation of a top-down decision approach)

EEW

EEW is a short-term risk-mitigation measure that acts as a triggering element for security and evacuation procedures included in the Organizational dimension of critical infrastructure and identified as influencing the absorption aspect of infrastructure resilience.

RRE

RRE is a post-event risk-mitigation and recovery measure for critical infrastructure affected by an earthquake. As a mitigation measure, it affects the organizational dimension of the preparedness aspect. In particular, RRE is partially included in

- Disaster Management plans,
- Disaster Management Human Resources plan.

As a recovery measure, RRE affects short-term actions included in all three infrastructure dimensions: organizational, technical, and operational.

In particular, it is supported by:

- Communication with external stakeholders,
- Collaboration with external stakeholders;

It triggers:

- The use of physical and human internal resources,
- The repairs of the n-th infrastructure service ;

It facilitates:

- The use of physical and human external resources;
- The reinstating of external resources required for the n-th infrastructure service.

6 SYSTEM DYNAMICS APPROACH

Introduction

This section of D5.1 discusses the theoretical background of a System Dynamics modelling process performed within WP5.2. The objectives of WP5 (listed in the introduction) are repeated here for context. They are to develop:

1. A set of qualitative and quantitative community resilience and recovery models and performance indicator metrics, which consider stakeholders' and community inter-relationships as well as cost/benefit models of preparedness and response actions for improved resilience (WP5.1 and WP5.2)
2. Algorithms for Decision Support Systems (DSSs) for real-time (OEF and EEW) and near-real-time (RRE) disaster prevention integrating frameworks, models, and datasets from WP3 and WP4 (WP5.3 and WP5.4)
3. Protocols for response, emergency management, and safety communication – including uncertainties, to technical stakeholders, non-technical stakeholders, and the public. (WP5.5)

The purpose of the System Dynamics Municipality Resiliency and Recovery model is to increase our understanding of municipality level resiliency and recovery. The model will have synergy with the DSSs (T5.3 and T5.4), which will integrate the various hazard, exposure, vulnerability assessment, and loss estimation model metrics developed in WP3 and WP4 with the individual stakeholders' and overall community performance metrics into planning and decision-making models.

The TURNkey platform will be a prototype of a dashboard that is intended to show information about the hazard during periods of increased hazards (OEF), information about an earthquake during an earthquake to provide Early Warning where possible (EEW), and Rapid Response information after an earthquake (RRE). The Rapid Response information will be corrected information for authorities, disaster/emergency management organizations on

1. The seismological characteristics of the earthquake (magnitude and location)
2. Spatial distribution of observed ground motion intensities
3. Spatial distribution of estimated damage and socio-economic losses, which is useful for disaster management.
4. Estimates of recovery trends and primary needs.

The TURNkey project members work in close collaboration with stakeholders to get their perspective on what should be displayed on the TURNkey dashboard. The System Dynamics Municipality Resiliency and Recovery model is designed to understand the views of decision-makers (e.g. municipality staff). The overall research question herein is asking what is important to decision-makers to best be of service to first responders, citizens, CI providers, and other businesses whose properties have been impacted. This question is asked within the boundaries set by the TURNkey project, the Icelandic TB, the municipality perspective, and conditions of Rapid Response to an earthquake (RRE).

The expected contributions of the System Dynamics Municipality Resiliency and Recovery model are three-fold.

- An understanding of stakeholder relationships, where the perspectives of the citizen and the municipality staff are placed at the centre.

- Municipality policy identification and implication, i.e., what policies are useful for resiliency and recovery, how and why
- Suggestions on what could be on the TURNkey dashboard that would be of interest to municipality staff.

Methodology

Systems Thinking

As explained by Dana Meadows (2008), a system is a set of things, such as people, cells, molecules, or whatever, which are interconnected in such a way that they produce their own pattern over time. The system may be buffeted, constricted, triggered, or driven by outside forces, but the system's response to these forces is characteristic of itself. Meadows further explains that a system consists of elements (physical or intangible), interconnections (physical, information, other), and function (purpose). Meadows makes the important distinction between purpose (function) and goals. The latter is what is intended, the former describes the system as it is. Systems theory looks at the structure and the behaviour of a system to understand how the system works, what makes poor results, and how to shift them into better patterns. Systems thinking helps to manage, adapt, and see the range of choices available.

Sverup et al. (2018) define System Science as the science of Systems Thinking, System Analysis, and System Dynamics, which all study causal relationships and feedback that enable us to analyse, sort-out and explain how changes come about under given conditions. While System Analysis help to understand events, processes, connections, System Dynamics leads to the modelling of systems, both conceptual mental models and mathematical models. Many problems are so complex, non-linear, and multi-dimensional that they require a non-linear approach to solving them. Sverup et al. emphasize the importance of never losing the understanding of the problem among all the details of the modelling process and equations.

The term systems thinking has been defined and redefined in many different ways since its coining by Barry Richmond in 1987 (Arnold and Wade, 2015). Arnold and Wade discuss what makes systems thinking so difficult to define? Why is it constantly redefined? What is missing? They suggest that the answer to defining the elusive concept of systems thinking in a way that will allow it to be measured. To this end, they proposed defining systems thinking by defining the application of systems thinking to itself: Systems thinking is a set of synergistic analytic skills used to improve the capability of identifying and understanding systems, predicting their behaviours, and devising modifications to them to produce desired effects.

System Dynamics

System Dynamics is a computer-based approach for policy analysis and design. It applies to dynamic problems arising in complex social, economic, ecological, and other systems. While dynamic problems are a function of time, System Dynamics problems also have a degree of complexity. Complex systems have multiple independent and connected components. Complexity in Systems Dynamics refers to accumulations and delays, feedback mechanisms, and non-linearities.

System Dynamics can be used to make predictions/estimations and it can also be used for back-casting from goals to make a design (Sverup et al., 2018). Back-casting is the design of the upfront causal end of a dynamic system to satisfy a back-end requirement.

The System Dynamics modelling process has multiple steps as outlined as follows. The first step is problem definition. This will include asking whether the problem at hand is indeed a System Dynamics problem. This is done by describing the dimensions of dynamic complexity accumulations, delays, feedback mechanisms, and non-linearities of the problem. For example, if there is no feedback

mechanism within the problem definition, System Dynamics methodology will not be able to solve the problem. Other aspects of problem definition include describing the problem in terms of one or more reference mode (Behaviour-Over-Time Graphs) and understanding the type of problem in terms of required analysis (learning, coordination, restructuring, and analysis). The second step is system conceptualization. During this step, Causal Loop Diagrams and Stock and Flow Diagrams are drafted to understand the cause and effects, identify feedback loops, and identify relationships between feedback loops, accumulation, and flow variables. The Stock and Flow diagram is the algorithm for the computer model. The third step is the model building itself using System Dynamics software. After an initial model is built, the model is validated and analysed in step four for behaviour such as loop dominance, and to ensure that the model functions as intended. Finally, in step 5, the model is ready to be used to evaluate policies and design new ones. To summarize, the process for building a System Dynamics computer simulation is an iterative process of problem definition, system conceptualization, model formulation, model validation and analysis, policy design, and evaluation.

System Dynamics models are useful in the management of projects, in particular large-scale projects. Sterman (1992) explains how feedback refers to the self-correcting or self-reinforcing side effects of decisions using construction projects as an example. When a construction project falls behind schedule, one possible managerial response is to increase the use of overtime. The extra hours help bring the project back on schedule, reducing the need for overtime in the future. Such a feedback process is self-correcting. However, if overtime remains high for an extended period, workers may become fatigued and burned out, leading to lower productivity, a higher rate of errors, and increased employee turnover, thus further delaying the project and leading to pressure for still more overtime, in a vicious cycle or self-reinforcing feedback process.

Disaster-Function Management Systems (DFM)

A performance metric is a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a stakeholder achieves its objectives. The performance metrics used in this study are those associated with DFM, as presented in D1.5 (Thorvaldsdóttir and Sigbjörnsson 2014, Thorvaldsdóttir 2016). DFM addresses resilience and recovery through a set of 8 disaster-related objectives and 33 objective-related procedures for reaching a disaster-related goal (see tables in appendix in D1.5). It is based on a theoretical statement of what disaster-related activities are, supported by a definition of a disaster-related goal. When developed, the basic method was centred around a societal level perspective but can be adjusted to any stakeholder perspective where managing risk, dealing with a situation, and learning from it are needed. The approach is underpinned by the theory of Management Functions and the principle of Management by Objectives, from classical management theory. DFM systems, therefore, lend themselves well to project management processes.

Using the DFM system approach, pre-disaster community resilience is measured by the ability of the community to understand risk, mitigate, prepare now for future operations, and learn from experience, or in other words:

- The effort taken to understand risk, is it the best of scientific evidence, or guesswork?
- The effort taken to mitigate risk. Is it based on a disaster risk scenario? Is it monitored?
- The effort taken to prepare for disaster operations, such as are there contingency plans and training? Based on preparedness, how long is recovery estimated to take?
- Finally, what is the ability of the system to learn? How adaptable is the system? Can it learn from its mistakes? Will it go back to the same normal, a better one or a worse one? How much effort does it take to learn? Will it learn automatically or does the issue have to be forced?

Through a System Dynamics analysis of the DFM system objectives and procedures, 28 inter-objective procedures were identified, totalling 58 procedures to be met to reach a disaster-related goal. These inter-objective related procedures highlight the need to understand how to go from one objective to another,

for example how to transfer from a contingency plan (written for the future) to an operations plan (to be activated now). A Stock and Flow Diagram was drafted that links the 58 procedures into one system with three main feedback loops (normal society, disrupted society, and changing society) that come together to create one system.

Municipality Level Resiliency and Recovery as a System Dynamics Problem

As stated earlier, the problem is first analysed to see whether it is indeed a System Dynamics problem. A short overview is now provided of how the problem of understanding municipality resiliency and recovery is defined as a System Dynamics problem.

Dynamic system: A response to a damaging earthquake is a function of time. The time scale is likely to be a few years.

Accumulation: Information that needs to be processed, people with problems due to their homes not being fully functioning, projects for municipality staff, and cost are examples of entities that accumulate after a damaging earthquake.

Delays: As projects for municipality staff increases, delays for the completion of projects will increase. This will lead to delays in problems being solved for citizens, calling for longer recovery and longer relief activities to bridge the gap till recovery is complete

Feedback: Stakeholder relationships are feedback relationships. Information is shared, used and feedback is given. Each stakeholder is an independent entity and the collection of stakeholders is a complex feedback system. The feedback process example given by Sterman (1992) can be adapted to a disaster recovery operations management project.

Reference modes: Reference modes are currently not available. Even the exact variables of interest have not been defined. Determining variables and reference modes is a key next step. They will be developed with stakeholders. The effort will start with a set of categories of variables and activities that can be used to explain a situation following an earthquake. Examples are given in the table below. These examples are likely to be too broad for the modelling, not all can be addressed. These are therefore a starting point and as the research evolves, the focus of the research and modelling will be narrowed, and the variables refined.

	Building	People	Municipality	Operations
1.	Load-bearing structure	Homeowner	Organization of staff	Impact
2.	Non-load bearing elements	Tenant	Number of staff	Lifesaving
3.	Building content	Food/drink	Efficiency of staff	Temporary relief
4.	Services to building	Work/income	Budget	Final recovery
5.	Services from building	travel	In place policies	
6.	Access to building	Health/social		

Table 24 Examples of reference modes

Research and Modelling Processes

It is considered good practice to build simple components of a model and then make sure it runs as intended before adding more components to it, thus building the model in stages. The System Dynamics Municipality Resiliency and Recovery model for TURNkey will be built in at least three distinct stages:

1. Modelling *normal life*. The daily life of municipality staff activity, the basic activities of a home, and the basic procedures of the other stakeholders involved in the Iceland TB will be modelled. This entails understanding their daily structure in terms of elements, connections, reference modes, and feedback loops. The focus here is not on modelling a problem, it is on modelling an existing system. In terms of System Dynamics structure model type, this is an Analysis problem (Hovmand, 2014).
2. Modelling *exogeneous excitation*. This is adding information from the TURNkey platform. These are factors that the stakeholders cannot control while they are happening, i.e., the earthquake itself and initial damages and consequences. The stakeholders could have controlled (i.e. mitigated) the risk before the earthquake, but not during. Any factors that are controllable are not exogeneous, but endogenous and become part of the system.
3. Modelling the *new operations structure* needed to manage the impact, lifesaving, relief, and recovery operations structure, i.e. *what* the daily structure should change into. Included in this step is a discussion of the transition from daily to disruption, i.e. *how* the daily structure changes into the new operations structure. In terms of System Dynamics structure model type, this is a Restructuring problem (Hovmand, 2014).

The modelling process of the System Dynamics Municipality Resiliency and Recovery model will use the objectives, processes, and loops from the DFM system that are relevant to the modelling based on the boundaries set by the TURNkey project, the Icelandic TB, the municipality perspective, and the Rapid Response to earthquake activities (RRE). Additional procedures will be added if needed.

The modelling will involve a combination of desk and field-based studies within the two Icelandic TB sites to identify factors and inter-relationships between stakeholders. The municipality will be placed as the main stakeholder, along with the citizens whose homes have been damaged, and the other Icelandic stakeholders are seen as service providers to help the community to run, thus having a multi-stakeholder system.

7 SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

This report constitutes a first step towards the development of a risk/resilience framework that can assess/demonstrate the impact of TURNkey on urban resilience. It also informs the further development of the TURNkey prototype, especially the work done on EEW, OEF, and RRE DSSs that will be presented in D5.3 and D5.4. The initial mapping of business organisational resilience and community resilience to the scorecard and rating system outlined in this deliverable will be validated through discussion with the TURNkey stakeholders as part of the second PAR research programme. Modelling of the potential impact of the TURNkey FWRC Platform on organisational resilience will be developed in Deliverable 5.2. The models will be applied in TURNkey TBs, e.g. the municipalities Hveragerði and Husavik in Iceland, and inform the further development of the TURNkey platform and decision-making toolbox.

8 REFERENCES

- Almufti, I., & Willford, M. (2014). The REDiTM rating system: A framework to implement resilience-based earthquake design for new buildings. In *10th US National Conference on Earthquake Engineering, Frontiers of Earthquake Engineering, July* (pp. 21-25). Available online at www.eeri.org/products-page/national-conference-on-earthquake-engineering/10th-u-s-national-conference-on-earthquake-engineering-frontiers-of-earthquake-engineering-proceedings-thumb-drive
- Arnold, R. D., & Wade, J. P. (2015). A definition of systems thinking: A systems approach. *Procedia computer science*, 44(2015), 669-678.
- Bakkensen, L. A., Fox-Lent, C., Read, L. K., & Linkov, I. (2017). Validating resilience and vulnerability indices in the context of natural disasters. *Risk analysis*, 37(5), 982-1004.
- Bartolucci A. Jones K. Deliverable 5.1: *Report on individual stakeholder and urban community performance metrics*. Version 1. Liquefact, 2017. Retrieved at www.liquefact.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D5.1-Report-on-Individual-Stakeholder-and-Urban-Community-Performance-Metrics.pdf
- Birkmann J (2013) *Measuring vulnerability to natural Hazards: towards disaster resilience societies*, Birkmann J Ed. United Nations University press, ISBN 978-92-808-1202-2
- Bruneau, M., Chang, S.E., Eguchi, R.T., Lee, G.C., O'Rourke, T.D., Reinhorn, A.M., Shinozuka, M., Tierney, K., Wallace, W.A. and Von Winterfeldt, D. (2003). A framework to quantitatively assess and enhance the seismic resilience of communities. *Earthquake spectra*, 19(4), 733-752.
- Chang, S.E., McDaniels, T., Fox, J., Dhariwal, R. and Longstaff, H. (2014), Toward Disaster-Resilient Cities: Characterizing Resilience of Infrastructure Systems with Expert Judgments. *Risk Analysis*, 34: 416-434.
- Cutter, S. L. (2016). The landscape of disaster resilience indicators in the USA. *Natural hazards*, 80(2), 741-758.
- Davis, C. A., & Giovinazzi, S. (2015, November). Toward seismic resilient horizontal infrastructure networks. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Earthquake Geotechnical Engineering, Christchurch, New Zealand* (pp. 2-4).
- Denyer D (2017) *Organisational resilience: a summary of academic evidence, business insights and new thinking*. BSI and Cranfield School of Management, available online at <https://www.cranfield.ac.uk/som/case-studies/organizational-resilience-a-summary-of-academic-evidence-business-insights-and-new-thinking>
- Earthquake Country Alliance (2016) *7 steps to a disaster resilient workplace*, Southern California Earthquake Centre at the University of Southern California. Available online at https://www.earthquakecountry.org/library/7_Steps_to_a_Disaster_Resilient_Workplace.pdf
- EPICC (2003) *Earthquake Planning for Business guide, Emergency Preparedness for Industry and Commerce Council*, ISBN No. 0-9732213-7-2 available online at www.iclr.org/wp-content/uploads/PDFS/earthquake-planning-for-business.pdf

- FEMA (2008) *QuakeSmart Business Toolkit* available online at www.fema.gov/media-library-data/1389803955572-35197e4e37a9950eaa391a9223cc970a/FEMA_P-811_QuakeSmart_Toolkit.pdf
- Fisher, R.E., Bassett, G.W., Buehring, W.A., Collins, M.J., Dickinson, D.C., Eaton, L.K., Haffenden, R.A., Hussar, N.E., Klett, M.S., Lawlor, M.A. and Millier, D.J (2010). *Constructing a resilience index for the enhanced critical infrastructure protection program* (No. ANL/DIS-10-9). Argonne National Lab.(ANL), Argonne, IL (United States). Decision and Information Sciences.
- Gibson CA and Tarrant M (2010) A 'conceptual models' approach to organisational resilience, *the Australian Journal of emergency management*. 25(2). Available online at <https://search.informit.com.au/fullText;dn=084520139241216;res=IELHSS>
- Han Z and Nigg J (2001) The Influences of Business and Decision Makers' Characteristics on Disaster Preparedness—A Study on the 1989 Loma Prieta Earthquake', *Int. J. Disaster Risk Sci.* 2011, 2 (4): 22–31.
- Holling CS (1973), Resilience and stability of ecological systems, *annual review of ecology and systematics* 4(1): 1-23
- Holling CS (1996) 'Engineering resilience versus ecological resilience', *engineering within ecological constraints*, National Academy of engineering, ISBN: 0-309-59647-5. Pp 31-44 Available online at: <http://www.environmentalmanager.org/wp-content/uploads/2008/03/holling-eng-vs-eco-resilience.pdf>
- Holling CS (2001) Understanding the Complexity of Economic, Ecological, and Social Systems, *Ecosystems*, 4: 390-405. DOI:10.1007/s10021-001-0101-5
- Hosseini, S., Barker, K., & Ramirez-Marquez, J. E. (2016). A review of definitions and measures of system resilience. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 145, 47-61.
- Hovmand, P.S: (2014). *Community based system dynamics*. New York, NY: Springer
- Jones K. Deliverable 1.4: *Report on Business Centric Use-Case Scenarios for CI and Local Business Stakeholder Groups*. TURNkey, 2020. Unpublished
- Kameda, H. (2000). Engineering management of lifeline systems under earthquake risk. *Bulletin of the New Zealand Society for Earthquake Engineering*, 33(3), 248-264.
- Lee, A. V., Vargo, J., & Seville, E. (2013). Developing a tool to measure and compare organizations' resilience. *Natural hazards review*, 14(1), 29-41. Available online at https://www.resorgs.org.nz/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/developing_a_tool_to_measure.pdf
- McDaniels, T., Chang, S., Cole, D., Mikawoz, J., & Longstaff, H. (2008). Fostering resilience to extreme events within infrastructure systems: Characterizing decision contexts for mitigation and adaptation. *Global Environmental Change*, 18(2), 310-318.
- McManus, S. (2008). *Organisational resilience in New Zealand*. Ph.D thesis, Univ. of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand
- Meadows, D. H. (2008). *Thinking in systems: A primer*. Chelsea green publishing.

- Mieler M, Paul N, Almufti I and Lee J (2018) Predicting earthquake-induced downtime in buildings: An overview of the state of the art', Proceedings of the 11th National Conference in Earthquake Engineering, Earthquake Engineering Research Institute, Los Angeles, CA. available online www.eeri.org/products-page/national-conference-on-earthquake-engineering/11th-u-s-national-conference-on-earthquake-engineering-integrating-science-engineering-and-policy-proceedings-thumb-drive-windows-only
- Morga, M., Pascale F. Wanigarathna, N., Majeed, Z., Meslem, A., and Jones K. (2020) Integrating mitigation to earthquake induced liquefaction disaster events into strategic built asset management planning. Liquefact, 2020. Available online at: www.liquefact.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/D5.4_bis.pdf
- Murnane, R., Simpson, A., & Jongman, B. (2016). Understanding risk: what makes a risk assessment successful?. *International Journal of Disaster Resilience in the Built Environment*.7(2): 186-200.
- OECD (2018) *Financial Management of Earthquake Risk* Available online at www.oecd.org/finance/Financial-Management-of-Earthquake-Risk.htm
- Omer, M., Mostashari, A., & Lindemann, U. (2014, January). Resilience Analysis of Soft Infrastructure Systems. In *CSER* (pp. 565-574).
- O'Rourke, T.D. (2007) Critical Infrastructure, Interdependencies, and Resilience. *The Bridge*, 37, 22-29.
- Preventionweb, (2020) *Vulnerability* www.preventionweb.net/risk/vulnerability
- Preventionweb (2020) *Resilience* <https://www.preventionweb.net/terminology/view/501>
- Proag, V. (2014). The concept of vulnerability and resilience. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 18, 369-376.
- Resilens. (2016) Deliverable 2.2: Qualitative, semi-quantitative and quantitative methods and measures for resilience assessment and enhancement. Available online at <http://resilens.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/D2.2-Methods-for-Resilience-Assessment-Final.pdf>
- Scholz, R. W., Blumer, Y. B., & Brand, F. S. (2012). Risk, vulnerability, robustness, and resilience from a decision-theoretic perspective. *Journal of Risk Research*, 15(3), 313-330.
- Sverup, H.U, Haraldsson, H, Koca, D., Belyazid, S, Olafsdottir, A.H., and Svensson, M (2018). *Systems Analysis and Systems Dynamics Modelling*, Icelandic System Dynamics Center, Háskólaprent, Reykjavík.
- Sterman, J. D. (1992). System dynamics modelling for project management
- Thorvaldsdottir, Solveig. (2016). Towards a Theoretical Foundation for Disaster-Related Management Systems: A System Dynamics Approach. Ph.D. dissertation, University of Iceland, 112pp, <http://hdl.handle.net/1946/24020>.
- Thorvaldsdottir, S., Sigbjörnsson, R. (2013). Disaster-function management: basic principles. *Natural Hazards Review*, 15(1): 48-57.
- Tiernan, A., Drennan, L., Nalau, J., Onyango, E., Morrissey, L., & Mackey, B. (2019). A review of themes in disaster resilience literature and international practice since 2012. *Policy design and practice*, 2(1), 53-74.

- Tierney, K. J., & Webb, G. R. (2001). Business vulnerability to earthquakes and other disasters. University of Delaware Disaster Research Centre DRC Preliminary Paper #320, available at www.researchgate.net/publication/209803485_Vulnerability_and_Risk_Assessment
- Tierney KJ (2007), Business and disasters: vulnerability, impact, and recovery, *Handbook of disaster research* – Rodriguez H, Quarantelli EL and Dynes RR (ed), Springer, available online at https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-0-387-32353-4_16
- UNDRO (1980): Natural disasters and vulnerability analysis, United Nations Disaster Relief Organisation, Geneva, available online at <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/95986?ln=en>
- UNDRR (2020) ‘Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Industrial and Commercial Buildings’, UNDRR available online at www.undrr.org/news/push-more-disaster-resilient-buildings-kicks-new-scorecard
- UNDRR (2015) The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, Available online at <https://www.undrr.org/publication/sendai-framework-disaster-risk-reduction-2015-2030>
- USGS (2020) New Earthquake Hazards Program. Lists, Maps, and Statistics. Available online at: <https://www.usgs.gov/natural-hazards/earthquake-hazards/lists-maps-and-statistics>
- Zhou, H., Wang, X., & Wang, J. A. (2016). A way to sustainability: Perspective of resilience and adaptation to disaster. *Sustainability*, 8(8), 737.

9 ANNEX A: THE ORGRES TOOL - QUESTIONNAIRE

This Annex shows the result a typical organisation might get when filling out the questionnaire linked to the ORGRES tool. As outlined in the section *Factors Affecting Business Resilience, Vulnerability and Adaptive Capacity to Earthquakes* (p. 29) the questionnaire is copyright of the Resilient Organisations Research Programme and has therefore not been represented here. However the latest iteration of the questions (July 2020) in the form of a resilience toolkit can be found at <http://orgrestool.resorgs.org.nz/orgres-tool/>

Well done!

You have taken the first step to building your organisation's resilience.

Your Resilience Score

75%

What does this mean?

This shows your organisation's rating for the 13 resilience indicators, from 1 (significant weakness) to 7 (significant strength), and 0 for unsure.

The 13 Resilience Indicators

Through in-depth case studies of organisations of different sizes, sectors, and ownership structures, research has identified 13 indicators of organisational resilience. These help to build business as usual effectiveness, as well as robust and agile response and recovery from crises.

How do I improve my resilience?

Below are some suggestions for improving your resilience for each of the 13 indicators. The highlighted boxes are the indicators your organisation scored lower in and are the key areas for you to be working on.

Leadership

Good leadership is critical for getting through a crisis. It is worth investing time and effort in building your ability to provide good management and decision making during challenges and times of adversity. This can be achieved through conducting regular exercises with your executive and ensuring lessons learnt are incorporated into plans as part of a continuous improvement programme. Consider establishing clear adversity leadership roles and responsibilities.

Staff Engagement

In a crisis, culture matters. It is important to have employees who understand the link between their own work, the organisation's resilience, and its long-term success. Employees should feel empowered to use their skills to solve problems. Consider how well information is shared with employees about emerging threats and how your organisation can adapt and respond to non-routine disruption.

Situation Awareness

Encourage employees to be vigilant about your organisation, its performance and potential problems. It is possible to build reliable foresight by establishing sentinels across the organisation who can use their networks to identify emerging threats. Encourage and reward employees for sharing good and bad news about the organisation including early warning signals that are quickly reported to organisational leaders.

Decision Making

While hierarchy/command and control may suit business as usual/steady state operations these structures may be broken in a major disruption. Consider establishing clear adversity leadership roles and responsibilities where employees have the appropriate authority to make decisions related to their work and authority is clearly delegated to enable a response. Ensure highly skilled employees are involved, or are able to make decisions where their specific knowledge adds significant value, or where their involvement will aid implementation.

Innovation and Creativity

Encourage and reward employees for using their knowledge in novel ways to solve new and existing problems, and for utilising innovative and creative approaches to developing solutions. Consider conducting adversity management exercises that stretch participants to encourage innovative solutions. Utilise scenarios where the solution is not known (non-routine) and involve varied and significant challenges.

Effective Partnerships

An understanding of the relationships and resources your organisation might need to access from other organisations during challenges or times of adversity will reduce impact and speed up recovery. Consider mapping supply chain vulnerabilities and tipping points where they would fail. Establish or participate in local industry mutual aid groups. Involve critical suppliers and regulators in adversity management exercises. Build strong networks with sector peers and emergency services.

Leveraging Knowledge

Lack of or inaccessible knowledge can lead to poor decision-making which can impact recovery. Ensure knowledge is captured and shared effectively throughout your organisation, with a strong focus on ensuring critical information is always available, with succession planning for key roles, an openness to learning, and drawing on internal and external expertise and lessons learnt when required. Consider conducting exercises to identify knowledge gaps. Following disruption events conduct a Post Incident Review/debrief of all significant incidents and keep a register of key learnings on the company internal website.

Breaking Silos

While silos can help establish focus within an organisation to improve performance they can also inhibit recovery when the operating paradigm is disrupted. Consider establishing multi-disciplinary adversity management teams. Conduct regular exercises that span across silos. Focus on building strong cooperative relationships and establishing common objectives. This will help reduce divisive social, cultural and behavioural barriers, which are most often manifested as communication barriers creating disjointed, disconnected and detrimental ways of working.

Internal Resources

If your organisation is stressed operating at business-as-usual the ability to recover from disruption is reduced. Invest in ensuring there are appropriate resources to operate your business - not only will your business perform better, but it also will build your capacity to absorb impacts from disruption events. Invest in cross-skilling between teams so that capacity can be ramped up or distributed.

Unity of Purpose

Many organisations that have survived a major disruption have one thing in common - a clear strong unity of purpose which is embraced by management and staff. Establish an organisation-wide awareness of what your organisation's priorities would be following a challenging or adverse event - ensure this is clearly defined at the organisation level, as well as an understanding of the organisation's minimum operating requirements. Develop a culture that sees challenge and adversity as an opportunity. Adverse events can be an excellent time to strengthen employee self-esteem, morale, and commitment.

Proactive Posture

To remain competitive an organisation must proactively identify emerging competitive threats or market opportunities. The same principle applies to adversity but sometimes does not have the same level of investment. Develop a strategic and behavioural readiness to identify and respond to early warning signals of change in the organisation's internal and/or external environment before they escalate into an adverse event. Develop policies and procedures that are principles based not rules based allowing staff to adapt them to make essential decisions.

Planning Strategies

Consider what your business would look like if you had to start from scratch following a disaster. What changes would you make to ensure it was less vulnerable? Consider identifying all critical processes, their dependencies and interdependencies, impacts of business disruption and any potential points of failure in the processes, infrastructure, people, assets, IT, data sets etc. Identify the required minimum service levels and potential tipping points where your response plans will be inadequate/exceeded by the impact of an adverse event. Identify potential alternative solutions.

Stress Testing Plans

Push the boundaries. A failed test is the best learning opportunity. Consider establishing a culture where failed tests are recognised and rewarded. Ensure this is backed up by a commitment and resources to address the failing and retest. Develop and conduct resource based adversity management exercises that stretch existing resource capabilities and require participants to look at new and innovative solutions. Utilise scenarios where the solution is not known (non routine) and involve varied and significant challenges to the Organisation. Include critical service providers as/where appropriate.

Interested in finding out more?

[Visit http://orgrestool.org/resources](http://orgrestool.org/resources)